

Arbitration and AI: The Role of LLMs in Drafting Awards

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Table of contents

Chapter 1: Introduction.....	2
§1.1: General introduction.....	2
§1.2: Methodology.....	4
§1.3: Delineation.....	4
§1.4: Academic relevance.....	4
§1.5: Structure outline.....	5
Chapter 2: Large Language Models and Arbitration.....	6
§2.1: Introduction.....	6
§2.2: The definition of LLMs and how they work.....	6
§2.3: The potential uses of LLMs in international arbitration.....	9
§2.4: Conclusion.....	11
Chapter 3: Large Language Models and Party Autonomy.....	12
§3.1: Introduction.....	12
§3.2: The intuitu personae principle and tribunal secretaries.....	14
§3.3: The scope of the tribunal's mandate.....	17
§3.4: The tasks of the arbitrators.....	18
§3.5: Which tasks are eminently personal?.....	20
§3.6: The connection between drafting and decision-making.....	27
§3.7: Arbitration rules on delegating the drafting of an award.....	31
§3.8: The comparability of LLMs and tribunal secretaries.....	36
§3.9: Conclusion.....	39
Chapter 4: Large Language Models and Confidentiality.....	40
§4.1: Introduction.....	40
§4.2: Confidentiality and the use of LLMs.....	41
§4.3: The training LLMs on awards and confidentiality.....	45
§4.4: Conclusion.....	47
Chapter 5: Large Language Models and the Award.....	48
§5.1: Introduction.....	48
§5.2: Formal requirements for awards and LLMs.....	50
§5.3: The Fourth Arbitrator defence.....	51
§5.4: Public Policy and LLMs in challenge procedures.....	56
§5.5: Conclusion.....	57
Chapter 6: Conclusion.....	58
Bibliography.....	60
Literature list.....	60
Case law list.....	76

Chapter 1: Introduction

§1.1: General introduction

‘The art of progress is to preserve order amid change, and to preserve change amid order.’¹

While this quote stems from 1929, it is still applicable today. In the past few years, the development of technology has started changing the world at a rapid pace. Whereas ten years ago food delivery robots were a thing of the future, it is now a reality that is becoming more and more common around the world.² The main change that threatens order at the moment, however, is generative artificial intelligence. Generative artificial intelligence is capable of generating text, images, video and sound.³ The launch of ChatGPT 3.0, a programme by the company OpenAI, made text-based generative artificial intelligence available to hundreds of millions of users all over the world.⁴ ‘Large Language Models’ such as ChatGPT are capable of reading, analysing and writing large volumes of text-based data and can often be integrated with other software to add to its use.⁵ Suddenly everyone was able to generate pages upon pages of relatively high quality writing and analysing huge amounts of data within seconds of pushing a button, threatening the job security of programmers, journalists and even paralegals.⁶ As Large Language Models get better and better, its role in the legal field becomes more and more pronounced.⁷ There is much debate in the legal field on the use of

¹ Alfred North Whitehead, *Process and Reality: An Essay in Cosmology* (Corrected edition, The Free Press 1978). Italicized for emphasis.

² ‘WATCH: Japan Rolls out “Cute” and “Lovable” Robots to Deliver and Serve Light Items like Food and Drinks’ (*Firstpost*, 8 February 2023)

<<https://www.firstpost.com/world/japan-rolls-out-cute-and-lovable-robots-to-deliver-and-serve-light-items-like-food-and-drinks-12120642.html>> accessed 3 January 2024.

³ Tom Taulli, *Generative AI: How ChatGPT and Other AI Tools Will Revolutionize Business* (Apress L P 2023) <<http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/ubnru-ebooks/detail.action?docID=30564687>>, p. 4.

⁴ Krystal Hu, ‘ChatGPT Sets Record for Fastest-Growing User Base - Analyst Note’ *Reuters* (2 February 2023) <<https://www.reuters.com/technology/chatgpt-sets-record-fastest-growing-user-base-analyst-note-2023-02-01/>> accessed 3 January 2024.

⁵ ‘Large Language Model (LLM)’ (*Techopedia*, 28 July 2023)

<<https://www.techopedia.com/definition/34948/large-language-model-llm>> accessed 5 January 2024.

⁶ Jacob Zinkula Mok Aaron, ‘ChatGPT May Be Coming for Our Jobs. Here Are the 10 Roles That AI Is Most Likely to Replace.’ (*Business Insider*)

<<https://www.businessinsider.com/chatgpt-jobs-at-risk-replacement-artificial-intelligence-ai-labor-trends-2023-02>> accessed 3 January 2024.

⁷ Dan Milmo, ‘Two US Lawyers Fined for Submitting Fake Court Citations from ChatGPT’ *The Guardian* (23 June 2023)

<<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2023/jun/23/two-us-lawyers-fined-submitting-fake-court-citations-chatgpt>> accessed 3 January 2024; ‘The Cautious Embrace between ChatGPT and Lawyers | Erasmus University Rotterdam’ <<https://www.eur.nl/en/news/cautious-embrace-between-chatgpt-and-lawyers>> accessed 3 January 2024; ‘ChatGPT and the Legal Profession’ <<https://www.ibanet.org/ChatGPT-and-the-legal-profession>>

accessed 3 January 2024; Tim Keary, ‘LLMs in the Legal Field: Transforming Legal Research and Analysis’ (*Techopedia*, 5 July 2023)

<<https://www.techopedia.com/llms-in-the-legal-field-transforming-legal-research-and-analysis>> accessed 3 January 2024; Greggworth, ‘Generative AI and the Small Law Firm: Leveling the Playing Field’ (*Thomson Reuters Institute*, 19 October 2023)

<<https://www.thomsonreuters.com/en-us/posts/legal/generative-ai-small-law-level-field/>> accessed 3 January 2024.

Large Language Models for tasks like legal research, fact-finding and drafting.⁸ Not only with regard to lawyers using Large Language Models, but also with regard to judges using it.⁹

In the world of international arbitration however, most of the current debate seems to focus on whether arbitrators could be replaced by artificial intelligence.¹⁰ While this is certainly an interesting topic, there seems to be a vacuum on whether arbitrators are allowed to use Large Language Models in the first place. Therefore, this thesis seeks to fill this void by answering the following research question:

To what extent and under which conditions is a tribunal allowed to use a Large Language Model to help draft an arbitral award in international arbitration?

In order to answer the research question, the following sub-questions will be discussed:

- ❖ What are Large Language Models, how do they work and what are their potential uses in international arbitration?
- ❖ What potential party autonomy-related risks and challenges may arise when an arbitral tribunal uses a Large Language Model in the drafting of an arbitral award?
- ❖ What potential confidentiality-related risks and challenges may arise when an arbitral tribunal uses a Large Language Model in the drafting of an arbitral award?
- ❖ What potential risks may arise regarding the validity, recognition and enforcement of awards drafted with the help of a Large Language Model?

⁸ Greggworth 2023; ‘It’s Not Automagical: Adopting Generative AI and Legal Tech Takes Strategy, Intuition, and Systems Thinking’ <<https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/in-the-balance/its-not-automagical-adopting-generative-ai-and-legal-tech-takes-strategy-intuition-and-systems-thinking>> accessed 3 January 2024; Tanguy Chau, ‘Council Post: Unlocking The 10x Lawyer: How Generative AI Can Transform The Legal Landscape’ (*Forbes*) <<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2023/08/16/unlocking-the-10x-lawyer-how-generative-ai-can-transform-the-legal-landscape/>> accessed 3 January 2024; Samuel Dahan and others, ‘Lawyers Should Not Trust AI: A Call for an Open-Source Legal Language Model’ (28 August 2023) <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=4587092>> accessed 23 November 2023.

⁹ Daniel Kellingley and Baroness Carr of Walton-on-the-Hill, ‘AI Judicial Guidance’ (Courts and Tribunals Judiciary December 2023).

¹⁰ Annabelle O. Onyefulu, ‘Artificial Intelligence in International Arbitration: A Step Too Far?’ [2023] *Arbitration: The International Journal of Arbitration, Mediation and Dispute Management* 56; Josephine Bhavani Rajendra and Ambikai S Thuraisingam, ‘The Deployment of Artificial Intelligence in Alternative Dispute Resolution: The AI Augmented Arbitrator’ (2022) 31 *Information & Communications Technology Law* 176; AG Shalaby, GM Abdelaziz and ME Kandeel, ‘Using Artificial Intelligence to Resolve Disputes through Online Arbitration’, 2022 *Ninth International Conference on Social Networks Analysis, Management and Security (SNAMS)* (2022).

§1.2: Methodology

The aforementioned questions will be answered through an analysis of case-law, legal history, legislation, literature and empirical data. This methodology is chosen to provide a holistic understanding of the legal, practical and theoretical aspects surrounding the use of Large Language Models in drafting arbitral awards.

§1.3: Delineation

This thesis will not discuss the upcoming EU Regulation on Artificial Intelligence (‘AI Act’) other than briefly mentioning it, as it is too early to tell what the regulation will contain in its final form and how it will be implemented.¹¹ Additionally, this thesis will limit itself to Large Language Models and not discuss other types of Artificial Intelligence due to a constraint in time and word count.

§1.4: Academic relevance

This thesis aims to find to what extent and under which conditions a tribunal is allowed to use a Large Language Model when drafting an arbitral award in international arbitration. The relevance of this research is borne out of the need for clarity that typically accompanies rapid technological developments. The mainstream launch of Large Language Models took the world by storm and its increasingly widespread use in the workforce has potentially massive implications. While the academic world produced numerous publications on Artificial Intelligence functioning as arbitrators, there is a distinct lack of research on the extent and under which conditions a tribunal is allowed to use a Large Language Model to help draft an arbitral award. This lack of clarity could have dire implications regarding the validity, recognition and enforcements of awards drafted with the help of a Large Language Model. Predictability presupposes clarity, and predictability in international arbitration is everything. This thesis aims to produce this clarity and as such improve the predictability in international arbitration when it comes to the use of a Large Language Model to help draft an award. Arbitrators, and by extension arbitration tribunals, will benefit from this as it helps them identify potential risks of using Large Language Models, which in turn helps them to take the necessary action to deliver valid awards and protect the privacy of the parties involved in their arbitration procedure. Knowing what risks should be mitigated also benefits arbitral institutions in drafting their arbitration rules. Moreover, users of arbitration will benefit in a similar fashion when drafting their arbitration agreement. Furthermore, users of arbitration will benefit indirectly from the action taken by arbitrators, arbitration tribunals and arbitral institutions to ensure the delivery of a valid award. Finally, this thesis also aims to encourage more discussion on the subject and to identify other gaps or existing uncertainties surrounding this topic, which can yield the aforementioned benefits as well.

¹¹ Video call with Pietro Ortolani to author (29 November 2023).

§1.5: Structure outline

The sub-questions, as laid down in paragraph 1.1, were devised in order to answer the main research question of this thesis. Each sub-question has its own chapter, with the final chapter being the answer to the main research question. Therefore, chapter 2 will discuss what Large Language Models are, how they work and what their potential uses are in international arbitration. Chapter 3 will examine potential party autonomy-related risks and challenges that may arise when an arbitral tribunal uses a Large Language Model in the drafting of an award. Chapter 4 will explore potential confidentiality-related risks and challenges that may arise when an arbitral tribunal uses a Large Language Model in the drafting of an arbitral award. Chapter 5 will cover potential risks that may arise regarding the validity, recognition and enforcement of awards drafted with the help of a Large Language Model. Finally, chapter 6 will draw a conclusion from all the previous chapters to answer the main research question.

Chapter 2: Large Language Models and Arbitration

§2.1: Introduction

This chapter examines what Large Language Models are and what their potential uses are in international arbitration. Paragraph 2.2 provides a definition of Large Language Models. Paragraph 2.3 discusses the potential uses of Large Language Models in international arbitration. Paragraph 2.4 draws a conclusion.

§2.2: The definition of LLMs and how they work

In order to define and understand what Large Language Models (hereafter: LLMs) are, it is important to take a step back and distinguish between the various concepts that surround it. First, there is Artificial Intelligence (hereafter: AI). There is a lack of consensus on the definition of AI, which requires this thesis to provide its chosen definition.¹² This thesis chooses to define AI as the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines.¹³ A subset of AI is Machine Learning, which is defined as AI with the ability to gain new knowledge from experience and perform activities not explicitly defined in its design or programmed instructions.¹⁴ A subset of Machine Learning is Deep Learning, which is defined as a type of Machine Learning that uses several steps, also called layers, to calculate a result.¹⁵ When this particular type of Machine Learning has all the layers required to fully calculate a result, this is referred to as an Artificial Neural Network.¹⁶ The term ‘Artificial Neural Network’ is derived from the way the layers function, which is inspired by how neurons function in human brain activity.¹⁷ Large Language Models (LLMs) in turn are a subset of Artificial Neural Networks and are generally defined as advanced computational models that are trained to predict words based on massive datasets of text.¹⁸ These datasets of

¹² Pei Wang, ‘On Defining Artificial Intelligence’ (2019) 10 *Journal of Artificial General Intelligence* 1.

¹³ A. B. Simmons and S. G. Chappell, ‘Artificial Intelligence-Definition and Practice’ (1988) 13 *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering* 14.

¹⁴ John D Kelleher, *Deep Learning* (MIT press 2019), p. 11-16; Was Rahman, ‘AI and Machine Learning’ in pages 1-19 (SAGE Publications Pvt Ltd 2024) <<https://sk.sagepub.com/books/ai-and-machine-learning>>; Google Cloud Tech, ‘Introduction to Large Language Models’ <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zizonToFXDs>> accessed 14 February 2024.

¹⁵ Kelleher (n 14), p. 65-68; Rahman (n 14); Google Cloud Tech, ‘Introduction to Large Language Models’ (n 14).

¹⁶ Kelleher (n 14), p. 8-10; Rahman (n 14).

¹⁷ Kelleher (n 14), p. 8-10; Rahman (n14); Google Cloud Tech, ‘Introduction to Generative AI’ <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G2fqAlgoPo>> accessed 16 February 2024.

¹⁸ Emily M Bender and others, ‘On the Dangers of Stochastic Parrots: Can Language Models Be Too Big?’, *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency* (ACM 2021) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3442188.3445922>> accessed 14 February 2024, p. 611; Steven T Piantadosi and Felix Hill, ‘Meaning without Reference in Large Language Models’ (2022) abs/2208.02957 ArXiv <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:251371595>>; Sam Bowman, ‘Eight Things to Know about Large Language Models’ (2023) abs/2304.00612 ArXiv <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:257913333>>, par. 5; Idan A Blank, ‘What Are Large Language Models Supposed to Model?’ (2023) 27 *Trends in Cognitive Sciences* 987; Yupeng Chang and others, ‘A Survey on Evaluation of Large Language Models’ (2024) 15 *ACM Trans. Intell. Syst. Technol.* <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3641289>>, p. 4-5.

text are often internet-based and are extracted from a variety of sources, ranging from e-books to Wikipedia to posts on public fora such as Reddit and social media platforms like Twitter.¹⁹ The datasets are then pre-processed in order to standardise the text and sanitise the contents.²⁰ Then, the datasets are fed to the neural network and are given billions of parameters to minimise the difference between the model's predictions and the actual data.²¹ The parameters are subsequently optimised for computational performance in the so-called pre-training phase.²² LLMs function in a typical input-output fashion. The user writes a so-called 'prompt' in natural language text that describes the task the LLM should perform and submits it to the LLM. The LLM then generally uses its layers to 'understand' the prompt and generate a text-based response.

The training phase of LLMs can differ wildly per LLM, but its main purpose is to teach the model how to predict words or tokens accurately.²³ Another purpose is to attach semantic context to each word in order to make the LLM capable of nuance in its output. The training phase can also include improving the LLMs' computational efficiency and developing certain methodologies that lead to better knowledge extraction from the same datasets.²⁴ An important training method for LLMs is called 'supervised learning'. Supervised learning uses training datasets that are labelled.²⁵ The labelling of datasets in this context essentially means that words are given a label that contains the context of that word.²⁶ This allows the LLM to 'understand' the context of the word better and to use it more appropriately in its response. This deserves an example to illustrate. Imagine that you have never seen an owl. You are then given a book that contains many pictures of owls, with each of these pictures being labelled as 'owl'. If you are shown a picture of an owl that is not in the book, you can use the labelled examples of owls in the book to determine whether the new picture contains an owl or not. The labelling of data, however, costs a lot of time, effort and money.²⁷ Thus, LLMs can also be given a limited number of labelled examples on how to perform a certain task. This is called a 'few-shot model'. There are, however, also LLMs that are exclusively trained on

¹⁹ Bender and others (n 18), p. 613; Jaromir Savelka and Kevin D Ashley, 'The Unreasonable Effectiveness of Large Language Models in Zero-Shot Semantic Annotation of Legal Texts.' (2023) 6 *Frontiers in artificial intelligence* 1279794, p. 6.

²⁰ Hugo Touvron and others, 'LLaMA: Open and Efficient Foundation Language Models' (2023) abs/2302.13971 ArXiv <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:257219404>>.

²¹ Bender and others (n 18), p. 618.

²² Aakanksha Chowdhery and others, 'PaLM: Scaling Language Modeling with Pathways' (2022) 24 *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 240:1.

²³ Zhengbao Jiang and others, 'How Can We Know What Language Models Know?' (2020) 8 *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics* 423; Bender and others (n 18), p. 611; Savelka and Ashley (n 19), p. 2.

²⁴ Yuntao Bai and others, 'Training a Helpful and Harmless Assistant with Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback' (2022) abs/2204.05862 ArXiv <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:248118878>>; Savelka and Ashley (n 19), p. 2.

²⁵ 'What Is Supervised Learning? | IBM' (5 April 2024) <<https://www.ibm.com/topics/supervised-learning>> accessed 6 May 2024.

²⁶ 'What Is Data Labeling? | IBM' (28 March 2024) <<https://www.ibm.com/topics/data-labeling>> accessed 6 May 2024.

²⁷ *ibid.*

unlabelled datasets. This is referred to as ‘unsupervised learning’.²⁸ Whereas supervised learning LLMs essentially receive labelled datasets on a silver platter, so-called ‘zero-shot models’ have to use auxiliary information to learn and perform. Taking the owl example again, imagine that instead of receiving a book with example pictures of owls, you only receive a basic description of an owl. A huge head, a stocky body, soft feathers, a short tail, and a reversible toe that can point either forward or backward.²⁹ When you are given a picture of an owl, you essentially have to understand the concept of an owl to identify the owl in the picture. Likewise, zero-shot models are trained on general tasks and concepts. When zero-shot models are prompted to perform a task they have never seen examples of, they will attempt to apply the learned concepts in order to perform the new task.³⁰ This ‘conceptual learning’ of LLMs is often referred to in the larger discussion on whether LLMs are actually capable of understanding language or not.³¹ This discussion will be touched upon in paragraph 3.8.

When an LLM is trained to perform tasks in a specific domain, it is called ‘fine-tuning’.³² Essentially, a successful fine-tuning transforms an LLM from a generalised model to a specialised model. This improves the accuracy of the LLM in the performance of specialised tasks, which is especially important in domains where accuracy is valued highly, such as the legal field.³³ A cost-effective alternative to fine-tuning and extensive training, is Retrieval-Augmented Generation, commonly abbreviated as RAG.³⁴ Essentially, the LLM is granted access to an index of external sources that provide real-world data authored exclusively by humans. Subsequently, this real-world data is used to supplement the generation of the LLM’s response to the prompt. In other words, LLMs can access and utilise accurate, up-to-date and domain-specific information through RAG.

Whereas RAG allows an LLM to access external sources, LLMs can also be integrated with other software.³⁵ By integrating an LLM with image recognition software (‘OCR’), text-to-image software like DALL-E or scheduling and case-managing software like Uncover, one can extend the capabilities of an LLM far beyond just text.

²⁸ ‘What Is Supervised Learning? | IBM’ (5 April 2024) <<https://www.ibm.com/topics/supervised-learning>> accessed 6 May 2024.

²⁹ ‘About Owls | Owl Research Institute’ (*owlresearchinstitute*) <<https://www.owlresearchinstitute.org/owls-1>> accessed 6 May 2024.

³⁰ ‘What Is Zero-Shot Learning? | IBM’ (11 April 2024) <<https://www.ibm.com/topics/zero-shot-learning>> accessed 6 May 2024.

³¹ Piantadosi and Hill (n 18); Chang and others (n 18).

³² Daniel M Ziegler and others, ‘Fine-Tuning Language Models from Human Preferences’ (2019) abs/1909.08593 ArXiv <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:202660943>>.

³³ Jason Wei and others, ‘Finetuned Language Models Are Zero-Shot Learners’ (2021) abs/2109.01652 CoRR <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.01652>>.

³⁴ Yizheng Huang and Jimmy X Huang, ‘A Survey on Retrieval-Augmented Text Generation for Large Language Models’ (2024) <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:269188036>>.

³⁵ ‘Large Language Model (LLM)’ (*Techopedia*, 28 July 2023) <<https://www.techopedia.com/definition/34948/large-language-model-llm>> accessed 5 January 2024.

In conclusion, the simple view would be that LLMs take in a great amount of data and use fancy statistics to ‘understand’ the prompt and generate a response to that prompt.³⁶ As LLMs continue to evolve, however, it has become too reductionist to view LLMs as just statistical word-predictors.³⁷ Through RAG, zero-shot learning and integration with other software, LLMs can be much more than just that.

§2.3: The potential uses of LLMs in international arbitration

As mentioned in paragraph 1.1, the use of LLMs has become increasingly widespread in the workforce around the world. In the light of continued improvement of LLMs, this trend of adoption in a professional context has permeated the legal field as well.³⁸ This is unsurprising, considering the fact that LLMs can currently assist legal practitioners in a variety of tasks. Through RAG, LLMs are capable of accessing authoritative external sources on law and can thus potentially aid legal practitioners or arbitrators with legal research.³⁹ Through integration with Image Recognition software, LLMs are currently capable of assisting legal practitioners with document and data analysis, e-discovery, and data extraction.⁴⁰ Moreover, LLMs integrated with scheduling and case-managing software can help legal practitioners and arbitrators with scheduling hearings and setting time limits. Furthermore, it is not unthinkable that LLMs are capable of assisting in the drafting of an award, as legal practitioners are already using LLMs to help them draft other legal documents.⁴¹ Indeed, the legal field as a whole has started to use LLMs, and international arbitration does not seem any different. In the first and only survey of the use of AI in international arbitration, it was found that 28% of the respondents had used ChatGPT in a

³⁶ Sam Bowman, ‘Eight Things to Know about Large Language Models’ (2023) abs/2304.00612 ArXiv <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:257913333>>, par. 3.

³⁷ *ibid*; Piantadosi and Hill (n 18); Idan A Blank, ‘What Are Large Language Models Supposed to Model?’ (2023) 27 Trends in Cognitive Sciences 987.

³⁸ ‘Thomson Reuters Report Highlights Legal Departments’ View of Technology, Artificial Intelligence’ <<https://www.thomsonreuters.com/en/press-releases/2017/october/thomson-reuters-report-highlights-legal-departments-view-of-technology-artificial-intelligence.html>> accessed 18 February 2024; Dan Milmo, ‘Two US Lawyers Fined for Submitting Fake Court Citations from ChatGPT’ *The Guardian* (23 June 2023) <<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2023/jun/23/two-us-lawyers-fined-submitting-fake-court-citations-chatgpt>> accessed 3 January 2024; Greggworth, ‘Generative AI and the Small Law Firm: Leveling the Playing Field’ (*Thomson Reuters Institute*, 19 October 2023) <<https://www.thomsonreuters.com/en-us/posts/legal/generative-ai-small-law-level-field/>> accessed 3 January 2024; ‘The Cautious Embrace between ChatGPT and Lawyers | Erasmus University Rotterdam’ <<https://www.eur.nl/en/news/cautious-embrace-between-chatgpt-and-lawyers>> accessed 3 January 2024; ‘ChatGPT and the Legal Profession’ <<https://www.ibanet.org/ChatGPT-and-the-legal-profession>> accessed 3 January 2024; Tim Keary, ‘LLMs in the Legal Field: Transforming Legal Research and Analysis’ (*Techopedia*, 5 July 2023) <<https://www.techopedia.com/llms-in-the-legal-field-transforming-legal-research-and-analysis>> accessed 3 January 2024;

³⁹ ‘Chaffetz Lindsey Talks Jus AI Assistant: Insights from Early Access Program Participants - Daily Jus’ (3 May 2024) <<https://dailyjus.com/news/2024/05/chaffetz-lindsey-talks-jus-ai-assistant-insights-from-early-access-program-participants>> accessed 16 May 2024.

⁴⁰ ‘Lawyers harnessing the power of AI’ (*Thomson Reuters Institute*) <<https://legal.thomsonreuters.com/content/dam/ewp-m/documents/legal/en/pdf/reports/lawyers-harnessing-power-of-ai.pdf>> accessed 3 January 2024, p. 10-13.

⁴¹ *ibid*.

professional context.⁴² The same survey reports that 85% of the respondents ranked saving time as the main perceived benefit of the use of AI. Additionally, 60% of the respondents ranked cost effectiveness as the most or second most important perceived benefit. In the light of the foregoing, it is extremely likely that the use of LLMs in international arbitration will only continue to grow.

While the benefits could potentially be great, it is important to identify the potential risks and challenges that could arise from the use of LLMs in international arbitration, especially with regard to arbitral tribunals using an LLM to help draft an award. The first risks that come to mind are that LLMs are prone to inaccuracies and hallucinations.⁴³ In a recent case, two lawyers used ChatGPT to write a court case filing, in which ChatGPT provided completely wrong information and even made up entire cases that never existed.⁴⁴ It goes without saying that arbitral tribunals should ensure that there is no inaccurate or fake information in the arbitral award they deliver.

Another risk is bias. Bias can be defined as a factor or series of factors ‘which appear to be irrelevant to the merit of our choices, but affect them nonetheless’.⁴⁵ Some authors define bias in a manner that is more specific to arbitration, namely as ‘extra-legal factors that affect decision-making’.⁴⁶ Such factors could be personal, social or institutional, to name a few.⁴⁷ Even judges, and by extension undoubtedly arbitrators too, are not above these extra-legal factors affecting their decision-making. In 2011, a large empirical study was published on the effects of extra-legal factors on the decision of judges on parole applications in Israel. The researchers found evidence that suggests that judges are significantly more likely to render a more favourable decision to the prisoners if the judge had taken a meal break right before the case.⁴⁸ While LLMs do not take meals, they do currently suffer from almost every bias in the book, despite efforts to curb this.⁴⁹ The main cause of this is that LLMs are trained on data made by humans, which causes the LLMs to ‘soak up’ the biases of the creators of said data.⁵⁰ Consequently, this can cause LLMs to be unreliable in analysing data or weighing

⁴² De Werra J and others, ‘The Use of AI in International Arbitration Proceedings’ (Digital Law Center, 5 December 2023).

⁴³ Milmo (n 38); ‘The Cautious Embrace between ChatGPT and Lawyers | Erasmus University Rotterdam’ <<https://www.eur.nl/en/news/cautious-embrace-between-chatgpt-and-lawyers>> accessed 3 January 2024; ‘ChatGPT and the Legal Profession’ <<https://www.ibanet.org/ChatGPT-and-the-legal-profession>> accessed 3 January 2024.

⁴⁴ Milmo (n 38).

⁴⁵ Maxi Scherer, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Legal Decision-Making: The Wide Open?’ [2019] *Journal of International Arbitration* 539.

⁴⁶ This is paraphrased from how bias is described in the following two sources: Myriam Gicquello, ‘Biased or Not Biased? Arbitral Decision-Making and Arbitrators’ Preferences’ (2022) 13 *Journal of International Dispute Settlement* 348; Stavros Brekoulakis, ‘Systemic Bias and the Institution of International Arbitration: A New Approach to Arbitral Decision-Making’ (2013) 4 *Journal of International Dispute Settlement* 553.

⁴⁷ One can also categorise such factors as ‘psychological, political and social’. See to that effect: Gicquello (n 46).

⁴⁸ Shai Danziger, Jonathan Levav and Liora Avnaim-Pesso, ‘Extraneous Factors in Judicial Decisions’ (2011) 108 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 6889.

⁴⁹ Partha Pratim Ray, ‘ChatGPT: A Comprehensive Review on Background, Applications, Key Challenges, Bias, Ethics, Limitations and Future Scope’ (2023) 3 *Internet of Things and Cyber-Physical Systems* 121.

⁵⁰ *ibid.*

evidence.⁵¹ Most importantly, if arbitrators use an LLM to help draft an award, inherent biases of LLMs could potentially influence the decision-making of arbitrators and thus the outcome of the arbitration. The potential influence that the use of an LLM to help draft an award could have on arbitral decision-making, will be discussed in paragraphs 3.6 and 3.8.

There are also other potential risks and challenges that intersect with core characteristics of international arbitration, such as party autonomy and confidentiality. Additionally, there are potential risks and challenges that could have dire implications regarding the validity, recognition, and enforcements of awards drafted with the help of LLMs. These potential risks and challenges will be addressed in the subsequent chapters.

§2.4: Conclusion

Large Language Models (LLMs) are a subset of Artificial Neural Networks and are generally defined as advanced computational models that are trained to predict words based on massive datasets of text. They function in a typical input-output method by providing a text-based response to a user prompt. The capabilities of LLMs can be extended through certain training methods and fine-tuning. These capabilities can be further enhanced through RAG and integration with other software. In international arbitration, LLMs can potentially be used for a variety of tasks, such as the drafting of an award, legal research, the scheduling of hearings, setting time-limits, document and data analysis, e-discovery and data extraction. The potential risks and challenges that could arise from the use of LLMs, however, should not be overlooked. Aside from LLMs being prone to inaccuracies, hallucinations and biases, there could also be dire implications regarding the validity, recognition, and enforcements of awards drafted with the help of LLMs.

⁵¹ Ghazal Bhootra and Ishan Puranik, ‘Arbi(Traitor)?: A Case against AI Arbitrators’ (2022) 4 Indian Arbitration Law Review 29, p. 38-40.

Chapter 3: Large Language Models and Party Autonomy

§3.1: Introduction

This chapter examines potential party autonomy-related risks and challenges that may arise when an arbitral tribunal uses an LLM to help draft an arbitral award. This paragraph sets out some preliminary remarks on party autonomy. Paragraph 3.2 outlines the *intuitu personae* principle and draws a preliminary comparison between the role of an LLM and the role of the tribunal's secretary to help draft an award. Paragraph 3.3 discusses the scope of the tribunal's mandate. Paragraph 3.4 provides an overview of the tasks of arbitrators. Paragraph 3.5 considers which of those tasks are eminently personal. Paragraph 3.6 discusses the drafting of an award and its connection to arbitral decision-making. Paragraph 3.7 examines certain commonly chosen arbitration rules for possibly restricting the use of LLMs by tribunals in the drafting of an award. Paragraph 3.8 evaluates whether the preliminary comparison between tribunal secretaries and LLMs from paragraph 3.2 was fair. Paragraph 3.9 draws a conclusion.

Party autonomy plays a very important role in arbitration.⁵² Party autonomy refers to the principle that parties are free to design their own arbitration procedures to tailor to their particular needs and preferences.⁵³ This means that not only parties can decide *when* to use arbitration, they can also decide *how* to arbitrate.⁵⁴ In order to enter arbitration, parties must have an agreement to arbitrate.⁵⁵ This agreement is binding on the parties.⁵⁶ Parties can enter into an agreement to arbitrate before or after a dispute has arisen between the parties.⁵⁷ The agreement can contain a number of clauses. The clauses that concern the '*how*' to arbitrate are the ones that could interfere with the extent to which arbitral tribunals can use LLMs to help draft awards. This involves the choice of the arbitral seat, the choice of the applicable substantive law, the choice of an arbitral institution and/or procedural rules, and the selection of arbitrators.⁵⁸ The arbitral seat is located in the State where the arbitral proceedings are legally taking place and can be chosen by the parties.⁵⁹ The arbitration procedure is subject to the laws that apply to arbitration in that State.⁶⁰ This is called the *lex arbitri*.⁶¹ This *lex arbitri* often contains so-called 'fall-back mechanisms' that provide basic procedural rules if the

⁵² Tony Cole and Pietro Ortolani, *Understanding International Arbitration* (2020), p. 4-5.

⁵³ *ibid.*

⁵⁴ To a certain extent, of course. See to that effect: *ibid.*, p. 7, 33-36.

⁵⁵ *ibid.*, p. 6.

⁵⁶ *ibid.*, p. 53.

⁵⁷ *ibid.*, p. 61-62.

⁵⁸ 'The Anatomy of an Arbitration Agreement | Global Law Firm | Norton Rose Fulbright' <<https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/en/knowledge/publications/d667d800/the-anatomy-of-an-arbitration-agreement>> accessed 7 March 2024; *ibid.*, p. 61-70.

⁵⁹ Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 29-31.

⁶⁰ *ibid.*, p. 30.

⁶¹ *ibid.*, p. 30.

parties did not choose any procedural rules that provide a solution to a procedural issue.⁶² *Lex arbitri* can also contain mandatory rules of public policy that parties cannot override.⁶³ Parties can also agree to choose to arbitrate under the auspices of a particular arbitral institution. This often means that the procedural rules of that arbitral institution, called institutional rules, are applicable. The parties can choose to make slight adjustments to these institutional rules insofar the institution allows it. If the parties did not select an arbitral institution, this is called an *ad hoc* arbitration.⁶⁴ In an *ad hoc* arbitration, parties can design their own procedural rules or select a set of procedural rules without selecting an arbitral institution.⁶⁵ Procedural rules, much like the *lex arbitri*, also often contain fall-back mechanisms. The parties can also make one of the most important decisions in arbitration: selecting the arbitrators.⁶⁶ This can involve determining the number of arbitrators, establishing a selection procedure of the arbitrators, and/or directly appointing specific individuals to serve as arbitrators in the arbitration procedure.⁶⁷ The ability to select arbitrators is a core component of arbitration and for good reason. The arbitrators together form the arbitral tribunal that delivers the award in the arbitration procedure. Arbitral awards are recognisable and enforceable around the world and can only be challenged based on limited grounds, relating to due process and public policy.⁶⁸ This is in contrast with regular civil procedures where appeals can be on substantive grounds. While arbitrators are generally bound to apply the applicable substantive law in the arbitration procedure, the limited grounds for appeal can preclude an appeal on the sole ground that an arbitrator did not apply the law correctly.⁶⁹ Consequently, the experience, knowledge, skills, reputation and potential biases of the selected arbitrators can be of great influence on the award rendered.⁷⁰

⁶² *ibid*, p. 30-35.

⁶³ Piotr Wilinski, *Excess of Powers in International Commercial Arbitration: Compliance with the Arbitral Tribunal's Mandate in a Comparative Perspective* (Eleven International Publishing 2021), p. 414.

⁶⁴ Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 15.

⁶⁵ Parties often opt for the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law Arbitration Rules, as this ruleset does not contain provisions that can only be executed by a specific arbitral institution. If parties select a ruleset with provisions that require a specific arbitral institution to act, but this institution is not involved with the arbitration, then those provisions cannot be applied. *ibid*, p. 105.

⁶⁶ Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 101-102.

⁶⁷ *ibid*, p. 100-104.

⁶⁸ J Ole Jensen, 'Secretaries to Arbitral Tribunals: Judicial Assistants Rooted in Party Autonomy Empirical Studies on the Role and Influence of Judicial Assistants and Tribunal Secretaries: Academic Article' (2020) 11 *International Journal for Court Administration* 1, p. 2.

⁶⁹ *ibid*, p. 6-7. See also Jeff Waincymer, 'International Arbitration and the Duty to Know the Law' (2011) 28 *Journal of International Arbitration*.

⁷⁰ David Hacking, 'Arbitration Is Only as Good as Its Arbitrators' [2011] *International arbitration and international commercial law: synergy, convergence and evolution: liber amicorum Eric Bergsten*; Nigel Blackaby and others, *Redfern and Hunter on International Arbitration* (Sixth edition, Oxford University Press 2015), paras. 4.13-4.16. J Ole Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (First edition, Oxford University Press 2019), p. 208-211; Jensen, 'Secretaries to Arbitral Tribunals' (n 68), p. 7-9.

§3.2: The *intuitu personae* principle and tribunal secretaries

The selection or appointment of an arbitrator comes with the duty to perform certain tasks, which are referred to as the arbitrator's mandate. For the reasons mentioned in the previous paragraph, parties take great care to select arbitrators. In this context, the well-fitting phrase 'arbitration is only as good as its arbitrators' is often recalled by academics.⁷¹ At its core, this phrase belies the personal nature of the arbitrator's task. This holds true even if the parties delegate the selection of the arbitrators to a third party, as the parties still place their trust in the third party to select the arbitrators for their dispute with care.⁷² One can thus conclude that the selection of an arbitrator is tied to the arbitrator's person, which is what '*intuitu personae*' essentially means.⁷³ The *intuitu personae* principle entails that there are certain specific tasks in the arbitrator's mandate that are so interwoven with the identity of the arbitrator, that the delegation of such tasks would contravene the very act of selecting the arbitrator. These tasks together make up an arbitrator's personal mandate and are thus referred to as 'eminently personal' tasks. There is broad international consensus that the *intuitu personae* principle prohibits arbitrators from delegating their personal mandate to someone else.⁷⁴ The scope of this personal mandate and the extent of the prohibition to delegate it, however, are topics of less concordance.⁷⁵ For instance, it is generally accepted that the administrative and organisational tasks of the arbitrators or tribunal fall within the scope of the arbitrator's mandate, yet are not caught by the delegation prohibition.⁷⁶ Indeed, tasks that are part of the arbitrator's mandate, but are not eminently personal, are still delegable. The delegation of tasks of the arbitrator's mandate, however, remains controversial. This controversy stems from discord over the scope of the arbitrator's personal mandate and the extent of the prohibition to delegate such tasks.⁷⁷ For instance, a main point of contention concerned the use of tribunal secretaries to help draft awards. Arbitral tribunals employ tribunal secretaries to aid the tribunal in carrying out its mandate. Some critics, however, argue that delegating

⁷¹ Hacking (n 70).

⁷² Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 176-177.

⁷³ *ibid*; Constantine Partasides, 'The Fourth Arbitrator? The Role of Secretaries to Tribunals in International Arbitration' (2002) 18 *Arbitration International* 147, p. 147.

⁷⁴ More research is needed on which tasks require explicit consent and which tasks require implicit consent. Partasides (n 73), p. 147; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 184.

⁷⁵ Partasides (n 73); Hacking (n 70); Giacomo Marchisio, 'A Comparative Analysis of Consent Awards: Accepting Their Reality' (2016) 32 *Arbitration International* 331; Giacomo Marchisio, *The Notion of Award in International Commercial Arbitration: A Comparative Analysis of French Law, English Law, and the UNCITRAL Model Law* (Kluwer Law International 2017) <<http://www.kluwerarbitration.com/book-toc?toc=TOC-Marchisio-2017>>; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70); Olufunke Adekoya, 'When Does the Use of an Arbitral Secretary Detract from the "Intuitu Personae" Principle?' (2018) 20 *ICCA Congress Series* 744; Felix Dasser and Emmanuel O Igbokwe, 'Chapter III: The Award and the Courts, Efficient Drafting of the Arbitral Award: Traditional Ways Revisited – Lesson Learned from the Past?' in Christian Klausegger and others (eds), *Austrian Yearbook on International Arbitration 2019 (2019)* (Wolters Kluwer 2019).

⁷⁶ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 192-194; Schroeder and Junge (n 75).

⁷⁷ Jeffrey M Waincymmer, *Procedure and Evidence in International Arbitration* (Wolters Kluwer, Law & Business 2012), p. 445-446; Marchisio, 'A Comparative Analysis of Consent Awards' (n 75); Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 203-207; Annabelle O. Onyefulu, 'Artificial Intelligence in International Arbitration: A Step Too Far?' [2023] *Arbitration: The International Journal of Arbitration, Mediation and Dispute Management* 56; Dasser and Igbokwe (n 75); Schroeder and Junge, (n 75).

the drafting of an award to a tribunal secretary would be too interwoven with arbitral decision-making, a task often considered to be eminently personal to the arbitrator. The drafting of (parts of) the award would fall within the scope of the *intuitu personae* principle, because it would influence arbitral decision-making to an extent where the selected arbitrator(s) no longer discharge(s) their decision-making function sufficiently.⁷⁸ In other words, these critics claim that the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit the delegation of assisting in the draft of an award to tribunal secretaries.⁷⁹

Recalling the main research question of this thesis, it becomes pertinent to establish whether the *intuitu personae* principle prohibits arbitral tribunals from using an LLM to help draft an award. Although there is no case law or existing literature that addresses this particular question, one can frequently draw upon analogous issues from the past to devise solutions for the present. In the author's view, such an analogous issue could be the extent to which an arbitral tribunal can use a tribunal secretary to help draft an award.⁸⁰ Indeed, if the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit the delegation of assisting in the draft of an award to *someone* else, would the *intuitu personae* principle not prohibit such delegation to *something* else? Thus, a preliminary comparison can be drawn between LLMs and tribunal secretaries. To determine whether this comparison holds any merit, it must be determined whether the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit the delegation of assisting in the draft of an award to *someone* else in the first place. Subsequently, there must be an understanding of the reasons behind the outcome of the aforementioned. Finally, it must be determined whether these same reasons can apply to the use of LLMs. The merit of this comparison will therefore be revisited in paragraph 3.8.

To answer these points, a deeper understanding of the *intuitu personae* principle and its effects on tribunal secretaries is warranted. To begin, there are two complications to the *intuitu personae* principle that need to be addressed. The first complication concerns the question whether parties, through their consent, can create an exception to the *intuitu personae* principle. Nowadays, most authors will answer this question affirmatively, and with good reason.⁸¹ Akin to how the One Ring in Tolkien's trilogy 'Lord of the Rings' was forged in the fires of Mount Doom and could thus only be undone by those very same flames, so can the *intuitu personae* principle only be undone by that which created it. Indeed, the very existence of the *intuitu personae* principle is willed into this world by virtue of party autonomy. It is only logical that through party autonomy, this existence can be undone.⁸² Some authors argue, however, that the mission of adjudication would override party

⁷⁸ Waincymer, *Procedure and Evidence in International Arbitration* (n 77), p. 445-446; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 203-207.

⁷⁹ Waincymer, *Procedure and Evidence in International Arbitration* (n 77), p. 445-446; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 203-207.

⁸⁰ At a later stage of my research, I encountered an article wherein two authors drew a comparison between tribunal secretaries and the use of AI to check arbitrators on the potential influence of bias in their decision-making. See to that effect: Paul Cohen and Sophie Nappert, 'The March of the Robots' (2017) 12 *Global Arbitration Review*.

⁸¹ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 222.

⁸² *ibid*, p. 219-224.

autonomy as soon as the parties have invoked the legal mechanism of arbitration.⁸³ Much like the story of Victor Frankenstein, the creator would lose control over his creation and instead becomes controlled by it.⁸⁴ As paragraph 3.3 will show, there is now broad consensus that the underlying concepts of this theory are incorrect. Consequently, this theory misses its mark as well.⁸⁵

Having established that parties can create an exception to the *intuitu personae* principle through their consent, there is a second complication that needs to be touched upon. Which type of consent is required to delegate which tasks? There are differing views on the degree of consent that is required to allow an arbitrator to delegate their personal mandate to someone else. As this particular discussion is very much contingent on the scope of the arbitrator's personal mandate and the extent of the prohibition to delegate such tasks, it will be discussed jointly in paragraph 3.5.

Having discussed the two aforementioned complications, it can be useful to gain a peripheral understanding of whom arbitrators typically delegate to. As mentioned before, arbitrators typically delegate to tribunal secretaries. Arbitrators also typically delegate to tribunal-appointed experts, and fellow arbitrators within the same arbitral tribunal they are members of.⁸⁶ Tribunal-appointed experts are, as the term suggests, experts appointed by an arbitral tribunal in order to assist the tribunal by providing their expert opinion on matters within their expertise.⁸⁷ Consequently, a tribunal-appointed expert has to perform tasks such as reviewing evidence or requesting additional information from the parties. Arbitrators also typically delegate to their fellow arbitrators within the same arbitral tribunal. Contrary to tribunal-appointed experts and, coming up next, tribunal secretaries, there are some arbitration laws and rules in place that allow co-arbitrators to delegate tasks that are typically considered eminently personal.⁸⁸ Perhaps the most controversial recipient of an arbitrator's delegation of tasks is the tribunal secretary.⁸⁹ It has been well documented that the (current) users of arbitration particularly value swift proceedings at a low cost, yielding a convincing, correct and enforceable award.⁹⁰ At the same time, our entry into the digital age has increased

⁸³ Party autonomy would be overridden by the principle of the 'unity of the adjudicative mission'. This theory stems from the jurisdictional / adjudicative theory of arbitration. See Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 220.

⁸⁴ Victor Frankenstein creates a monster, the so-called 'Monster of Frankenstein'. Through a series of events, the monster decides to force Victor to create a female counterpart to the monster. Victor tries to avoid this by fleeing, but the monster keeps finding him. Eventually, the monster kills the wife of Victor on their wedding night. Victor pursues the monster in an attempt to exact vengeance on it but dies in his attempt. The tale ends with the creature mourning Victor and showing remorse over his crimes.

⁸⁵ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 222.

⁸⁶ Giovanni De Berti, 'Experts and Expert Witnesses in International Arbitration: Adviser, Advocate or Adjudicator' (2011) 318 *Austrian Yearbook on International Arbitration* 53, p. 54; Friederike Schäfer, 'Chapter II: The Arbitrator and the Arbitration Procedure - Practical Problems Arising from the Contractual Relationship between Expert and Participants in an Arbitration' (2011) 318 *Austrian Yearbook on International Arbitration* 113, p. 113; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 13-50.

⁸⁷ De Berti (n 86); Schäfer (n 86), p. 113.

⁸⁸ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 212-215.

⁸⁹ Schroeder and Junge (n 77).

⁹⁰ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 53-70.

the complexity and duration of international arbitration.⁹¹ Indeed, the sheer volume of documents and information in a contemporary international arbitration has been described as a ‘paper tsunami’.⁹² To counteract these changes, tribunals are increasingly resorting to employing tribunal secretaries in order to enhance the efficiency of international arbitration, in particular with regard to the duration, costs and quality of the arbitration.⁹³ The role of the tribunal secretary is, thus, one borne out of a need for speed, a craving for savings and a quest for best.⁹⁴ Unlike regular secretaries, tribunal secretaries are often junior or senior lawyers from the arbitrators’ law firm.⁹⁵ While tribunal secretaries have been around for many a century, the controversy surrounding its role is rather new.⁹⁶ Most of the controversy was sparked by the famous Yukos case, which holds the record for the largest sum awarded in international arbitration at a whopping fifty billion dollars.⁹⁷ In this case and subsequent appeals, the Russian Federation submitted that the arbitral tribunal acted in excess of its mandate by delegating their personal mandate to a tribunal secretary to such an extent, that the secretary could be viewed as a *de facto* ‘fourth arbitrator’.⁹⁸ In order to fully understand this claim, however, there is still some ground to cover. Therefore, this case will be discussed further in paragraph 3.5.

§3.3: The scope of the tribunal’s mandate

In practice, parties often choose either a sole arbitrator, or three arbitrators to form a tribunal.⁹⁹ When all the required arbitrators are selected or appointed, whether it be one, three or more, they form together an arbitral tribunal. It should be recalled that the *intuitu personae* principle concerns the personal mandate of an individual arbitrator. The personal mandates of all the arbitrators in an arbitral tribunal together are referred to as the tribunal’s mandate. The arbitrator’s mandate and the tribunal’s mandate are in this context to a certain extent interchangeable.¹⁰⁰ Naturally, the personal mandate is the tribunal’s mandate when it comes to sole arbitrators. In order to determine the scope of the tribunal’s mandate, there must first be an understanding of the nature and source of the tribunal’s mandate. There are diverging

⁹¹ Dasser and Igbokwe (n 77), p. 297.

⁹² Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 54.

⁹³ *ibid.*

⁹⁴ *ibid.*

⁹⁵ Philipp Peters, ‘Chapter II: The Arbitrator and the Arbitration Procedure - Presiding Arbitrator, Deciding Arbitrator: Decision-Making in Arbitral Tribunals’ in Nikolaus Pitkowitz and others (eds), *Austrian yearbook on international arbitration 2011* (Kluwer Law International), p. 151.

⁹⁶ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 24-26.

⁹⁷ *Yukos*, Court of The Hague 20 April 2016, ECLI:NL:RBDHA:2016:4230 (First instance court, the Netherlands); ‘The Yukos Appeal Decision on the Role of Arbitral Tribunal’s Secretaries’

<<https://www.ibanet.org/article/B55CB7F1-01C6-4BDF-9383-90F567C17147>> accessed 1 January 2024.

⁹⁸ *Yukos*, Court of The Hague 20 April 2016, ECLI:NL:RBDHA:2016:4230 (First instance court, the Netherlands); *Yukos*, District Court of The Hague 18 February 2020, ECLI:NL:GHDHA:2020:234 (Judgment on appeal, the Netherlands); *Yukos*, Supreme Court 20 February 2024, ECLI:NL:GHAMS:2024:351 (Judgment on high appeal, the Netherlands).

⁹⁹ Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 105-106.

¹⁰⁰ Note that this is only in reference to delegating tasks; when the *intuitu personae* principle forbids an arbitrator from delegating a task, it also forbids the arbitral tribunal from delegating this task. One could argue that this does not always hold up the other way, however.

views on this topic that are rooted in fundamental theories on arbitration as a whole.¹⁰¹ One theory, called the contractual theory, proposes that the arbitral process, and by extension the tribunal's mandate, solely stems from the arbitration agreement between the parties and their submissions when a dispute arises.¹⁰² An opposing view is the jurisdictional theory, which proposes that the States' monopoly on resolving disputes fully and finally is shared with the arbitral tribunals. The arbitrators would serve in a quasi-judicial capacity and have their power to adjudicate derived from the State. The parties would be merely invoking a legal mechanism with their arbitration agreement and submissions.¹⁰³ A third view combines the two theories and is therefore referred to as the 'hybrid' theory.¹⁰⁴ It proposes that while parties have the party autonomy to organise their arbitration process, the arbitration, and by extension the arbitral tribunal, has to operate within the limits imposed by *lex arbitri*.¹⁰⁵ To summarise, each of the aforementioned theories influences to what degree the tribunal's mandate is determined by party autonomy, respectively: fully, none and partially.¹⁰⁶ This in turn impacts the degree to which the arbitral tribunal can decide how to operate by themselves, the so-called 'tribunal autonomy'.¹⁰⁷ Nowadays, there is broad consensus that the hybrid view is the better view.¹⁰⁸ This essentially means that the scope of the tribunal's mandate is shaped by a balance between party autonomy and tribunal autonomy.¹⁰⁹ Likewise, the arbitrator's mandate is also shaped by that very same balance, as was put forth in paragraph 3.3.

As mentioned before, the scope of the tribunal's mandate depends on the scope of the arbitrator's mandate. Therefore, it is now pertinent to zero in on what the arbitrator's mandate actually entails. What exactly are the tasks of the arbitrators? And which of those tasks does the *personae intuitu* principle prohibit to delegate to others?

§3.4: The tasks of the arbitrators

As mentioned previously, the hybrid view on arbitration embraces both the contractual and adjudicative aspects of arbitration. As a result, the obligations of international arbitrators are derived from their contractual relationship with the parties and their adjudicative role.¹¹⁰ As

¹⁰¹ Günther J Horvath, 'The Duty of the Tribunal to Render an Enforceable Award' (2001) 18 *Journal of International Arbitration*, p. 137-138; Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 2-9; Wilinski (n 63), p. 464-465.

¹⁰² Horvath (n 101), p. 137-138; Wilinski (n 63), p. 464-465; Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 2-9.

¹⁰³ Horvath (n 101), p. 137-138.

¹⁰⁴ Horvath (n 101), p. 137-138; Wilinski (n 63), p. 464-465; Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 2-9.

¹⁰⁵ Horvath (n 101), p. 138.

¹⁰⁶ Wilinski (n 63), p. 457-458.

¹⁰⁷ *ibid*, p. 457-458.

¹⁰⁸ This is because arbitrators must apply the mandatory provisions of *lex arbitri*, which rules out the contractual theory. On the other hand, the jurisdictional theory ignores the wide power of party autonomy. Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 14.

¹⁰⁹ This is true for all three theories, but the balance points for the contractual theory and the jurisdictional theory are on each extreme of the scale. See Wilinski (n 63), p. 459-460.

¹¹⁰ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 174; Gary Born, *International Commercial Arbitration* (Third edition, Kluwer Law International 2021), par. 13.04 (Kluwer Law International, Updated February 2024).

remarked by academics before, there is a lack of authority on what those obligations actually are.¹¹¹ Authors that wrote on this topic generally seem to agree on two main obligations: conducting the arbitration and issuing an enforceable award.¹¹² The task of conducting the arbitration is tied to the organisational and administrative tasks that rest on the arbitrator. Among others, such tasks can be to receive and deal with correspondence of parties, to organise and schedule meetings or to manage appointments.¹¹³ While some authors consider setting dates for hearings and deadlines as purely administrative tasks, other authors argue that such tasks should be categorised as procedural tasks.¹¹⁴ This distinction is important, as will be shown in the next paragraph. Procedural tasks include starting the proceedings and can include deciding on the language and seat of the arbitration.¹¹⁵ It may also include taking procedural decisions, such as setting page and time limits, hearing dates, ordering interim measures, and conducting oral hearings.¹¹⁶ Additionally, the arbitral tribunal has to ensure that it has the jurisdiction to decide all the issues before it. This means that the arbitrators need to check the arbitrability of the issues and whether the arbitration agreement is valid.¹¹⁷ Procedural tasks also include preventing a violation of due process.¹¹⁸ While there are some divergences between jurisdictions on which requirements of due process must be met in arbitration, at its core it comes down to ‘fair’ and ‘equal’ treatment, plus the ‘reasonable opportunity’ to present one’s case.¹¹⁹ This includes failing to keep a party informed of communications or developments in the arbitration.¹²⁰

Finally, the arbitrators need to sign and date the award and deliver it to the parties in compliance with the relevant law or rules.¹²¹ In the author’s opinion, heeding proper procedure, even though being connected to conducting the arbitration, has more to do with ensuring the enforceability of the award. Events where the arbitral procedure does not meet the parties’ agreement or the law of the seat can lead to a denial of recognition and enforcement or the setting aside of that award.¹²²

¹¹¹ *ibid.*

¹¹² Horvath (n 101), p. 139-148; Waincymer, *Procedure and Evidence in International Arbitration* (n 69), p. 97-102; Adekoya (n 75); Schroeder and Junge (n 75), p. 21 - 41.

¹¹³ Adekoya (n 75).

¹¹⁴ Waincymer, *Procedure and Evidence in International Arbitration* (n 69), p. 445-446; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 192-194.

¹¹⁵ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 192.

¹¹⁶ *ibid.*, p. 192-193.

¹¹⁷ Article V(1)(a) Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (adopted 10 June 1958, entered into force 7 June 1959) 330 UNTS 3 (hereafter: New York Convention); Born, *International Commercial Arbitration* (n 110), chapter 26 (Kluwer Law International, Updated March 2024).

¹¹⁸ See for example: with regard to the right to be heard, see Article 24(1) United Nations Commission on International Trade Law Model Law (hereafter: ‘Model Law’ or ‘ML’) and Section 34(2)(h) English Arbitration Act 1996 (hereafter: English AA). With regard to the right to be treated fairly and impartially and the reasonable opportunity to present its case, see Section 68 jo. 33 English AA; ‘Arbitration Awards – Due Process and Procedural Irregularities: Challenges’ (*Fieldfisher*) <<https://www.fieldfisher.com/en/insights/arbitration-awards---due-process-and-procedural-ir>> accessed 16 April 2024.

¹¹⁹ Fieldfisher (n 118).

¹²⁰ Domestic courts have the discretion whether or not to refuse recognition and enforcement of the award when this article is applicable. Article V(1)(b) New York Convention; Horvath (n 101), p. 145.

¹²¹ Blackaby and others (n 70), par. 9.16.

¹²² Horvath (n 101), p. 145.

The task of issuing an enforceable award leads to several crucial subtasks which deserve to be mentioned. Often considered the primary task leading to the issuance of an enforceable award is decision-making, as this produces the decision in the award. Importantly, many authors consider that arbitral decision-making at its core requires that a tribunal has ‘independently formed its view as to the key evidentiary matters, as to the applicable law and has come to form its own fully informed and reasoned view as to the basis of the determinations and orders it wishes to make’.¹²³ While arbitrators are generally bound to apply the applicable substantive law in the arbitration procedure, the limited grounds for appeal can preclude an appeal on the sole ground that an arbitrator did not apply the law correctly.¹²⁴ Indeed, some courts have held that awards may be set aside if an arbitrator has ‘manifestly disregarded the law’ or ‘manifestly disregarded evidence’.¹²⁵ It follows that arbitral decision-making requires arbitrators to perform legal research and legal analysis. Arbitral decision-making will be discussed in more depth in paragraph 3.6.

To render an enforceable award, the tribunal must apply the public policy and mandatory provisions of the law of the seat.¹²⁶ As mentioned before, this includes procedural tasks that can affect the enforceability of the award. It also includes meeting formal requirements for an award, such as the requirement that the award should be in writing.¹²⁷ Depending on the jurisdiction, there are other formal requirements for an award. For example, Article 31(1) of the Model Law requires that arbitrators sign the award. Both the Model Law and the Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes between States and Nationals of Other States (hereafter: the ICSID Convention) require that an award contains reasons for the decision stated in the award.¹²⁸ In the light of the foregoing, it is clear that the award must be drafted, which is another task of the arbitrator.¹²⁹ The drafting of an award will be discussed more thoroughly in paragraph 3.6.

§3.5: Which tasks are eminently personal?

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, the tasks of conducting the arbitration and the issuance of an (enforceable) award are considered to be the main tasks of the arbitrator. Conducting the arbitration is mostly related to organisational and administrative tasks, like the planning and scheduling of hearings. These tasks are widely considered to not be caught

¹²³ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 198-199, 208.

¹²⁴ Jensen, ‘Secretaries to Arbitral Tribunals’ (n 68), p. 6-7. See also Waincymer, ‘International Arbitration and the Duty to Know the Law’ (n 69).

¹²⁵ Horvath (n 101), p. 146.

¹²⁶ Article V(2)(b) New York Convention.

¹²⁷ Article IV(1)(a) New York Convention; Section 52 of the English AA and Article 42(1) of the Stockholm Chamber of Commerce Rules form an exception to this requirement. See also: ‘The Arbitral Award: Form, Content, Effect’

<<https://globalarbitrationreview.com/guide/the-guide-challenging-and-enforcing-arbitration-awards/3rd-edition/article/the-arbitral-award-form-content-effect>> accessed 5 May 2024.

¹²⁸ Article 48(3) and Article 52 (1)(e) of the ICSID Convention 1965, entered into force 1966. Also Article 31(2) of the Model Law, but it provides an exception for consent awards.

¹²⁹ Dasser and Igbokwe (n 75), p. 296.

by the *personae intuitu* principle.¹³⁰ As such, they are often delegated to tribunal secretaries. Some authors, however, argue that the way arbitration is conducted decisively influences the outcome on the merits.¹³¹ In other words, certain procedural tasks should be viewed as a part of arbitral decision-making. Accordingly, it is argued that tasks relating to procedural discretion coloured by the arbitrator's identity are thus eminently personal.¹³² Conversely, procedural issues that are definitively determined by party agreement, the applicable rules, or *lex arbitri* fall outside the scope of the *personae intuitu* principle. This is a sound argument, as it is precisely that personal nature of the arbitrator's tasks that the *personae intuitu* principle prohibits from delegating.

The task of issuing an enforceable award is an even more complicated task. The issuance of an award presupposes that the tribunal has made a decision and has recorded this decision in said award by drafting it. It is widely accepted that arbitral decision-making is eminently personal, as the arbitrators are specifically chosen by the parties to use their discretion to decide and render an enforceable award. But what is considered to be decision-making? Is the drafting of an award part of arbitral decision-making? Especially the latter was a central question in the Yukos case, as paragraph 3.2 briefly remarked. In this case, the Russian Federation submitted that the arbitral tribunal acted in excess of its mandate by delegating their personal mandate to a tribunal secretary to such an extent, that the secretary could be viewed as a *de facto* 'fourth arbitrator'. In the same line of reasoning, the Russian Federation claimed that the arbitration tribunal was not constituted correctly, as the 'fourth arbitrator' was neither selected nor appointed by the parties. The Russian Federation based their claims on three arguments. The first argument was that the secretary, Valasek, spent a disproportionate amount of hours compared to the arbitrators. The second argument was that the tribunal delegated tasks of a substantive nature to the secretary without prior consent of the parties. The third argument was that the secretary allegedly drafted between 41-70 percent of the arbitral award, which, according to the Russian Federation, would indicate Vaselek's participation in the decision-making process of the arbitrators.¹³³

The Dutch Supreme Court rejected both claims, stating that there was no evidence of Valasek's participation in the decision-making process. The Court took the view that the amount of hours spent on the case, nor the percentage of the award drafted by the secretary implied any participation in the decision-making process. Indeed, the Court stated that a tribunal secretary drafting the text of an arbitral award does not mean that the secretary participated in the decision-making process. Per the Court, the choice of the tribunal to use these texts in the award does not amount to a (sufficiently serious) breach of the *intuitu*

¹³⁰ Adekoya (n 75); Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 192.

¹³¹ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 193. Jensen argues that this also applies to procedural matters such as decisions on time limits and scheduling of the hearings. Peters, however, says these are purely administrative matters. See to that effect: Peters (n 95), p. 142.

¹³² Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 190-192.

¹³³ *Yukos*, Court of The Hague 20 April 2016, ECLI:NL:RBDHA:2016:4230 (First instance court, the Netherlands). See also subsequent appeal: *Yukos*, District Court of The Hague 18 February 2020, ECLI:NL:GHDHA:2020:234 (Judgment on appeal, the Netherlands), par. 6.6.

personae principle, even if the text remains unedited. Crucially, the Court ruled that if there is no explicit agreement between the parties regarding the use of secretaries to help draft an award and the substantive decision-making was carried out exclusively by the arbitrators without any third party influence, then the arbitral tribunal has the autonomy to decide to what extent it wishes to use a secretary to help draft the award.¹³⁴ Furthermore, the Court notes that if it is true that the tribunal only introduced Valasek as an assistant and contact person to the parties, then the tribunal did not fully inform the parties about the nature of the functions carried out by Valasek. The Court does not consider this failure to inform to meet the threshold of a sufficiently serious excess of mandate. Finally, the Court rejects the claim that the tribunal was constituted incorrectly. The Court argues that the award was only signed by the three arbitrators of the tribunal and not by the supposed ‘fourth arbitrator’. Consequently, the Court sees no grounds for annulment.

There are three key takeaways to gather from this Dutch court case. The first takeaway is that the drafting of an award by a tribunal secretary does not amount to substantive decision-making. The second takeaway is that the *intuitu personae* principle does not prohibit delegating the drafting of an award insofar the substantive decision-making was exclusively carried out by the arbitrators without any third party influence. The third takeaway is that when it comes to the employment of a tribunal secretary, the point of departure is tribunal autonomy. When party autonomy is explicitly exercised on the matter, it generally restricts tribunal autonomy on that matter. The Dutch Court does remain vague on whether it constitutes a ‘less-than-sufficiently-serious’ breach of the *intuitu personae* principle if the arbitrators use unedited text, drafted by the tribunal secretary, as the award. In any case, such a scenario would not be sufficiently serious to risk the enforceability of the award.

It is interesting to compare the Yukos judgment to the role of the earlier discussed tribunal-appointed expert and the delegation of tasks between fellow arbitrators. It can be tempting for the tribunal to defer to the expert’s opinion even though the tribunal should remain in charge.¹³⁵ Indeed, one could imagine that the more a tribunal needs to rely on an expert to understand facts of the case, the more likely it becomes that a tribunal defers to the expert’s opinion. Some authors have raised concerns on whether this could be construed as the tribunal *de facto* delegating their arbitral decision-making to the expert. Those concerns are in part mitigated due to the fact that many rules and provisions require the tribunal to discuss the appointment of such an expert with the parties first.¹³⁶ Indeed, specific and

¹³⁴ *Yukos*, District Court of The Hague 18 February 2020, ECLI:NL:GHDHA:2020:234 (Judgment on appeal, the Netherlands), par. 6.6.14.1.

¹³⁵ *Sacheri v. Robotto*, Corte di Cassazione, 2765, 7 June 1989, Y.B. Com. Arb. XVI (1991), 156–157 (Supreme Court, Italy). In this case an award is challenged in an annulment procedure. The claim is based on a violation of the *intuitu personae* principle and a violation of due process. The arbitral tribunal had appointed an expert to make the arbitral decision and draft the award for them, as the tribunal lacked the legal skills to draft an award. This total abdication of arbitral decision-making and drafting of the award was of course seen as a violation of the *intuitu personae* principle.

¹³⁶ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 13-50; De Berti (n 86), p. 54; Bernardo M Cremades Román and Patricia Peterson, *Rethinking the Paradigms of International Arbitration* (International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) 2023) <<https://www.kluwerarbitration.com/document/TOC-Cremades-2023>>, chapter 7.

informed consent is often required.¹³⁷ In those cases, parties can exclude the aforementioned risk entirely by withholding their consent to the appointment of an expert. Party autonomy is thus the point of departure. This contrasts with the third takeaway from the Yukos case, where the point of departure regarding tribunal secretaries was tribunal autonomy.

Concerning the delegation of tasks between fellow arbitrators within a tribunal, arbitrators may not delegate the ‘core of decision-making’ to other tribunal members.¹³⁸ Each arbitrator must have applied the law to the facts and have reached an independent decision.¹³⁹ Arbitral decision-making will be discussed further in paragraph 3.7. Distinct from arbitral decision-making, it is important to note that the entire task of drafting may be delegated to one of the co-arbitrators.¹⁴⁰ But, this must not lead to the delegation of the ‘core of decision-making’ as stated earlier. While some authors argue that at the end of the arbitration, the award must ‘reflect the collective mind of the collegial body that makes up the panel’, others acknowledge that formally only the signature of the arbitrators are required.¹⁴¹ Contrary to the role of the tribunal secretary, however, there is a much greater degree of acceptance for this internal division of labour.¹⁴² This is unsurprising, as both the delegator and the recipient of the delegation were selected either directly or indirectly by the parties. In other words, all the arbitrators of the tribunal are legitimised by specific and informed party consent. While this consent may not extend to an internal division of labour, it is certainly more legitimising than an arbitrator delegating their mandate to someone whom parties have not consented to at all. In comparison to the Yukos case, however, arbitrators seem to be afforded a somewhat similar leeway as tribunal secretaries.

Of course, the judgment in the Yukos case does not mean that the controversy is now solved. Not only should the Yukos judgment hold up to scrutiny, the very notion of what is deemed to be an eminently personal task should too. As mentioned previously, the tasks of conducting the arbitration and in particular substantive decision-making are widely considered to be eminently personal tasks. But how does the ‘award by consent’ fit into this? First, it is important to consider that there is no internationally accepted definition of an award.¹⁴³ Indeed, both the New York Convention and the ICSID Convention do not give a definition on awards. Born from this lack of international consensus, the ‘award by consent’ is considered to be a strange animal. Just like litigation in national courts, parties can settle their issues with a settlement agreement during arbitration proceedings.¹⁴⁴ The parties then have two choices at

¹³⁷ See to that effect: Article 26 ML; Cremades Román and Peterson (n 136), chapter 7.

¹³⁸ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 214.

¹³⁹ *ibid.*

¹⁴⁰ Jensen argues both the first statement and begrudgingly agrees with the second. See to that effect: Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 214. Conversely, Dasser only puts forth the first statement. See to that effect: Dasser and Igbokwe (n 75), p. 297.

¹⁴¹ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 214.

¹⁴² Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 212. Alternatively, some authors consider that arbitrators' delegation of powers to one of the other arbitrators in a multi-member tribunal should be limited to administrative tasks or procedural decisions. See to that effect: Peters (n 95), p. 145.

¹⁴³ Blackaby and others (n 70), par. 9.05.

¹⁴⁴ *ibid.*, par. 9.35.

their disposal.¹⁴⁵ The first is to discontinue the arbitration through revoking the arbitral tribunal's mandate. This results in the loss of jurisdiction and powers conferred upon the tribunal by the parties involved.¹⁴⁶ The second is to encapsulate the settlement agreement in an award.¹⁴⁷ By 'packaging' the settlement within an award, one can use the New York Convention or the ICSID Convention as a 'vehicle' to make the recognition and enforcement of the settlement agreement easier.¹⁴⁸ Though the ICSID Convention does not specifically mention consent awards, the International Centre for the Settlement of Investment Disputes (hereafter: ICSID) Arbitration Rules do explicitly allow them.¹⁴⁹ In combination with Article 54(1) of the ICSID Convention, this gives consent awards the same status as any other ICSID arbitral award.¹⁵⁰ Failure to enforce an ICSID award would be a breach of the Convention.¹⁵¹ In the USA, a New York district court held in 2017 that there is no reason that a consent award would be considered any less binding under the New York Convention than a regular award.¹⁵² Consequently, the recognition and enforcement of consent awards in investment arbitration are rather straightforward. It is important to note for later, however, that the annulment ground of ICSID awards that requires the award to contain reasons, is disapplied when it comes to consent awards.¹⁵³ Recognition and enforcement of consent awards under the New York Convention, thus pertaining to international commercial arbitration, are less straightforward. As mentioned before, the New York Convention does not include a definition of an award, nor explicitly or implicitly mentions consent awards. Per the *travaux préparatoires*, some States have requested that the Convention include consent awards explicitly, yet these requests were not discussed further.¹⁵⁴ While many leading jurisdictions in the field of international arbitration recognise consent awards as arbitral awards due to Article 30(1) of the UNCITRAL Model Law, the treatment of consent awards is thus not uniform.¹⁵⁵ Indeed, there are some significant divergences regarding the treatment of consent awards under international instruments and national arbitration acts.¹⁵⁶ In the USA, a New York district court held in 2017 that there is no reason that a consent award would be considered any less binding under the New York Convention than a regular award.¹⁵⁷ In

¹⁴⁵ Article 55 (2) of the ICSID Arbitration Rules 2022 and Article 30(1) UNCITRAL Model Law.

¹⁴⁶ Blackaby and others (n 70), par. 9.35. See to that effect: Article 55 (2) ICSID Arbitration Rules 2022.

¹⁴⁷ Blackaby and others (n 70), par. 9.36.

¹⁴⁸ Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 850.

¹⁴⁹ Article 55(2)(b) ICSID Arbitration Rules 2022.

¹⁵⁰ Yaraslau Kryvoi and Dmitry Davydenko, 'Consent Awards in International Arbitration: From Settlement to Enforcement' (2015) 40 Brooklyn Journal of International Law, p. 855.

¹⁵¹ Article 27 ICSID Convention.

¹⁵² *ALBtelecom v. Unifi Communications*, ALBtelecom SH.A v. Unifi Commc'ns, Inc., 16 Civ. 9001 (PAE), 10 (S.D.N.Y. May. 30, 2017) (Southern district court of New York, United States).

¹⁵³ Kryvoi and Davydenko (n 150), p. 855; Article 52(1)(e) ICSID Convention.

¹⁵⁴ In the following document as 'arbitral settlements': *Travaux préparatoires for the United Nations Conference on International Commercial Arbitration, Consideration of the Draft Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards*, E/CONF.26/L.26 (1957); and as 'amicable settlements' in the document: Secretary-General, *Travaux préparatoires for the United Nations Conference on International Commercial Arbitration, Activities of Inter-Governmental and Non-Governmental Organizations in the Field of International Commercial Arbitration*, E/CONF.26/4 (1958), 26.

¹⁵⁵ Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 109-110.

¹⁵⁶ *ibid*, p. 137.

¹⁵⁷ *ALBtelecom v. Unifi Communications*, ALBtelecom SH.A v. Unifi Commc'ns, Inc., 16 Civ. 9001 (PAE), 10 (S.D.N.Y. May. 30, 2017) (Southern district court of New York, United States).

France, the Code of Civil Procedure is applicable to foreign and international awards as France has set up a more favourable framework than the Convention itself.¹⁵⁸ As such, foreign or international consent awards are recognised and enforced under Article 1514 of the Code of Civil Procedure as long as the award was proven to exist and the enforcement order would not result in a manifest violation of international public policy.¹⁵⁹ France's attitude towards domestic consent awards, however, is significantly different. In this context, domestic awards are awards rendered in France that do not affect international trade.¹⁶⁰ Per the 'Cour de cassation', the act of recording a settlement without the arbitrator providing reasons, cannot amount to an adjudicative act.¹⁶¹ The lack of reasons is of course typical for consent awards, as it is the parties that resolve the dispute and not the arbitrators.¹⁶² Consequently, consent awards rendered in France are only regarded as mere transactions and not as awards.¹⁶³ In England, the Arbitration Act 1996, much like the French Code of Civil Procedure, is applicable to foreign and international awards due to being more favourable than the New York Convention. Similarly to Model Law jurisdictions, consent awards are treated in the same manner as any other award. As a result, the enforcement of foreign consent awards is no problem. Of note, however, is that consent awards do not need to include reasons under English law.¹⁶⁴ In the light of the above, one could argue that consent awards seem to conflict with the notion that the drafting of the reasons in an award is an eminently personal task. Indeed, if the arbitrator's mandate does not necessarily include the task of drafting of reasons, then how could the task be eminently personal? Admittedly, it is true that international arbitral consent awards that fall under English, French, American or UNCITRAL Model Law jurisdictions generally do not require the inclusion of reasons in consent awards. Yet, it is important to recall that consent awards come into being through the informed and specific consent of the parties to agree to settle the dispute in a certain way. In other words, under the ICSID and UNCITRAL Model Law, the task to provide reasons in the award is only suspended when both parties expressed their informed and specific consent to settle the dispute by consent award. Recalling that the origins of the arbitrator's personal mandate lie in party autonomy, one cannot cite consent awards to support the claim that the drafting of reasons is not an eminently personal task in international arbitration as a whole. Indeed, reasons remain a mandatory part of an award in the absence of informed and specific consent to settle a dispute by consent award.

How, then, do consent awards interact with the eminently personal task of substantive decision-making? Could the existence of consent awards prove that arbitrators do not always have the discretion to decide? One could interpret the ruling of a Texas district court in

¹⁵⁸ Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 132; Article VII(I) Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (adopted 10 June 1958, entered into force 7 June 1959) 330 UNTS 3 (hereafter: New York Convention).

¹⁵⁹ Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 132.

¹⁶⁰ *ibid*, p. 132.

¹⁶¹ *ibid*, p. 133.

¹⁶² *ibid*, p. 133.

¹⁶³ *ibid*, p. 133-134.

¹⁶⁴ *ibid*, p. 126-128; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 346.

support of that, as it held that ‘no binding or persuasive statutory language or case law requires a court to hold that a tribunal must reach its own conclusions, separate from the parties’ agreement, to make a valid, binding award subject to the Convention’.¹⁶⁵ The answer to this question, however, has to be negative, as the arbitrators always have the discretion to refuse to incorporate the settlement agreement into the award.¹⁶⁶ Notably, in cases where the settlement agreement would violate mandatory provisions of the law of the seat or the law of the State where the parties aim to enforce the award, this discretion becomes a duty to refuse the incorporation of the settlement agreement into the award.¹⁶⁷ To illustrate, consider the situation wherein two parties start the arbitration proceedings with the arbitral seat located in the Netherlands. The parties request the arbitrator to record their settlement agreement in which parties agree to form a cartel. This would violate Article 101 of the Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union, which is directly applicable and a mandatory provision of public order in any Member State of the European Union. As a result, the presiding arbitrator has the duty to refuse the request of the parties. The substantive decision-making thus remains in determining whether the settlement agreement adheres to the mandatory provisions of the law of the seat or the law where the parties aim to enforce the award.

Having discussed the role of consent awards, this paragraph will now turn to addressing the criticism and discord on eminently personal tasks and the *intuitu personae* principle on the whole. Some authors consider that specific and informed consent is required for the delegation of any task within the arbitrator’s mandate, including those that are not of a personal nature.¹⁶⁸ Other authors argue that the degree of consent should be relative to how likely it is that the delegation of the task affects the arbitral decision-making.¹⁶⁹ Then there are authors that propose that the personal nature of the arbitrator’s mandate should be rethought entirely.¹⁷⁰ Schultz and Kodac conducted a survey that showed that 65% of the parties did not care whether arbitrators delegated their tasks to someone else, including tasks such as issuing procedural orders and drafting the award.¹⁷¹ Consequently, Schultz and Kodac consider those results as an indicator that the role of the arbitrator is akin to that of a manager: ‘only responsible for the product, with no mandate to do the work themselves’.¹⁷² Recalling the origin of the *intuitu personae* principle, it is party autonomy expressed through the act of selecting an arbitrator that introduces the prohibition of delegating tasks falling

¹⁶⁵ *ALBtelecom v. Unifi Communications*, ALBtelecom SH.A v. Unifi Commc'ns, Inc., 16 Civ. 9001 (PAE), 10 (S.D.N.Y. May. 30, 2017) (Southern district court of New York, United States); Ava Borrasso, ‘U.S. District Courts Rule Consent Awards Fall Within New York Convention’ (*Kluwer Arbitration Blog*, 6 April 2018) <<https://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2018/04/06/u-s-district-courts-rule-consent-awards-fall-within-new-york-convention/>> accessed 12 May 2024.

¹⁶⁶ Marchisio, *The Notion of Award* (n 75), p. 133-134; Tony Cole and Pietro Ortolani, *Understanding International Arbitration* (2020), p. 179-180.

¹⁶⁷ Waincymer, *Procedure and Evidence in International Arbitration* (n 77), p. 186-189, 1024-1028; *Eco Suisse China Time Ltd v. Benetton International NV* Case C-126/97, ECR 1991, I-03055; Horvath (n 101).

¹⁶⁸ Schroeder and Junge (n 75).

¹⁶⁹ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 212-277.

¹⁷⁰ Thomas Schultz and Robert Kovacs, ‘The Rise of a Third Generation of Arbitrators?: Fifteen Years after Dezalay and Garth’ (2012) 28 *Arbitration International* 161, p. 170-171.

¹⁷¹ *ibid.*

¹⁷² *ibid.*

within the arbitrator's personal mandate. If parties do not expect their selected arbitrators to draft the award by themselves, then how can the task of drafting an award fall into the personal mandate of the arbitrator? Barring any applicable arbitration rules or mandatory provisions of the applicable procedural law that state otherwise, of course. This line of thought is further reinforced by the selection of the 'busy arbitrator'.¹⁷³ Much like popular singers and famous politicians, there are certain arbitrators that are highly sought-after. Naturally, this has consequences for the availability of such arbitrators, hence the adjective 'busy'. Consider how most popular singers and famous politicians delegate the writing of their songs and speeches to ghostwriters as they lack the time to do it all by themselves. Similarly, the busy arbitrator realistically lacks the time to carry out their arbitrator's mandate without delegating anything.¹⁷⁴ Consequently, parties cannot reasonably expect that the busy arbitrator they selected does not delegate the drafting of the award, provided that the parties were aware of the arbitrator's availability.¹⁷⁵ Additionally, paragraph 3.2 underlines the increasing complexity duration of international arbitration, warranting an ever greater need to delegate. In light of the foregoing, there is a strong argument to be made that the drafting of an award should no longer be considered a part of the arbitrator's personal mandate in contemporary international arbitration.

§3.6: The connection between drafting and decision-making

As noted in the previous paragraph, the two eminently personal tasks of an arbitrator are conducting the arbitration and making a substantive decision. One can argue whether ensuring the enforceability of the award should be categorised under the former or the latter task. In any case, chapter 5 will examine whether delegating the task to help draft an award could affect the enforceability of the award, which includes procedural grounds. Therefore, this paragraph will explore how arbitral decision-making corresponds with the drafting of a typical award. By identifying how arbitrators make their decisions, one can also identify how tribunal secretaries or LLMs can potentially influence arbitral decision-making by assisting in the drafting of an award. If certain parts of an award are integral to arbitral decision-making, then the drafting of those parts must be considered to fall under the eminently personal part of the arbitrator's mandate.

According to Jensen,¹⁷⁶ there are two modes of human decision-making: deduction and intuition.¹⁷⁷ Perhaps surprising to some, arbitrators are considered to be human.¹⁷⁸ Therefore, these modes also apply to arbitrators. Deduction corresponds with the typical 'analytical

¹⁷³ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 179-183.

¹⁷⁴ *ibid*, p. 179-183.

¹⁷⁵ *ibid*, p. 179-183. Many arbitration rules require the arbitrator(s) to disclose their availability prior to appointment or confirmation. See for example Article 11(2) of the International Chamber of Commerce Arbitration Rules 2021.

¹⁷⁶ Dr. Ole Jensen is a senior associate in the International Arbitration Practice Group of Wilmer Cutler Pickering Hale and Dorr LLP in London and Berlin.

¹⁷⁷ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 196.

¹⁷⁸ Rebecca K Helm, Andrew J Wistrich and Jeffrey J Rachlinski, 'Are Arbitrators Human?' (2016) 13 *Journal of Empirical Legal Studies* 666.

process of arriving at a decision’, also referred to as ‘legal formalism’.¹⁷⁹ Intuition refers to the influence that extra-legal factors have on the deduction process, also referred to as ‘legal realism’.¹⁸⁰ Some extra-legal factors have been discussed in paragraph 2.3, showcasing that even judges can be subject to the same biases as other humans. Thus, arbitrators are biased too.¹⁸¹ More research is needed on how an LLM would interact with any biases or other extra-legal factors that an arbitrator may harbour. When it comes to deduction, Jensen identifies five basic steps of arbitral decision-making:

- i) reading and listening to the parties' submissions, (ii) establishing the facts of the case, (iii) identifying the contents and meaning of the applicable law(s), (iv) applying the law to the facts, thus reaching a decision (usually in deliberations), and (v) recording this decision and its reasoning.¹⁸²

While each arbitration can differ greatly from the next, Jensen and others consider these five steps to be performed in any international arbitration, albeit in varying orders.¹⁸³ The manner in which these steps are performed, depends mostly on whether the tribunal consists of a sole arbitrator or multiple arbitrators.¹⁸⁴ Whereas the deliberations of a sole arbitrator take place in the arbitrator’s mind, the deliberations between multiple arbitrators requires intercommunication. It is important to note that the organisation of the deliberations is left to the arbitrators’ discretion.¹⁸⁵ Many arbitrators typically deliberate right after a hearing, given the fleeting nature of human recollection.¹⁸⁶ Other arbitrators argue to the contrary, as such an approach could overemphasise witness evidence as opposed to document evidence. Instead, deliberations should be held at a later stage of the arbitration, using transcripts of the hearings.¹⁸⁷ Deliberations are held informally or formally, depending on the degree of collegiality of the tribunal.¹⁸⁸ Informal deliberations can happen over dinner or even tequila shots. Formal deliberations often consist of the chairperson leading the deliberations and structuring the common understandings of the arbitrators into a ‘tribunal working paper’, eventually serving as the basis for the drafting of an award.¹⁸⁹

¹⁷⁹ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 196; Maxi Scherer, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Legal Decision-Making: The Wide Open?’ [2019] *Journal of International Arbitration* 539, p. 566-567.

¹⁸⁰ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 196; Scherer, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Legal Decision-Making’ (n 179), p. 567-569.

¹⁸¹ Helm, Wistrich and Rachlinski (n 178); Myriam Gicquello, ‘Biased or Not Biased? Arbitral Decision-Making and Arbitrators’ Preferences’ (2022) 13 *Journal of International Dispute Settlement* 348.

¹⁸² Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 197. See also Peters (n 95).

¹⁸³ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 197; Peters (n 95); Jingzhou Tao, ‘Chapter 33: Deliberations of Arbitrators’ in Patricia Shaughnessy, Sherlin Tung and Pierre A Karrer (eds), *The powers and duties of an arbitrator: liber amicorum Pierre A. Karrer* (Kluwer Law International 2017), p. 349-358.

¹⁸⁴ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 202-203.

¹⁸⁵ Peters (n 95), p. 148.

¹⁸⁶ *ibid*, p. 148.

¹⁸⁷ Tao (n 183), p. 354-355.

¹⁸⁸ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 200-202.

¹⁸⁹ A ‘chairperson’ or ‘presiding arbitrator’ is an arbitrator that is nominated or appointed to lead the tribunal. Peters (n 95); *ibid*, p. 200-202.

This brings us to the fifth step: drafting the award. But what exactly is considered to be the drafting of an award? As mentioned previously, the formal requirements for an award only require the signatures of the arbitrators, the place of arbitration and a reasoning.¹⁹⁰ There are no specific guidelines or laws on how specific and detailed the reasoning must be.¹⁹¹ As mentioned in paragraph 3.5, consent awards do not even need to contain reasons at all. Consequently, the length of an award can range from a few pages to several hundred pages long.¹⁹² There are, however, some soft-law instruments in the form of a checklist that recommend a general structure of an award.¹⁹³ The typical structure of an award contains the following parts: (i) information on the parties, counsel and the arbitrators, (ii) procedural history of the arbitration, (iii) relevant facts of the case, (iv) parties' positions, (v) reasoning, (vi) the decision (*dispositif*) and (vii) remaining formalities.¹⁹⁴ So how does the drafting of an award correspond with arbitral decision-making? Some authors argue that the drafting of an award is strictly recording the decision-making process and therefore not really a part of arbitral decision-making.¹⁹⁵ Others argue that the drafting of an award is intrinsically linked to the decision-making process, making it fall (partly) within the scope of the *intuitu personae* principle.¹⁹⁶ Drafting the award would be a continuous process throughout the duration of the arbitration that would influence the decision-making process and *visa versa*.¹⁹⁷ Both views have their merits, in the author's opinion. On one hand, one could envision the process of drafting an award to be akin to writing a master thesis. A reiterative process of writing and rewriting, constantly re-evaluating one's stance on the matter. On the other hand, it could simply be a summary of what has been decided. Both situations can arise, as the organisation of the deliberations and the drafting of an award is left to the arbitrators' discretion.¹⁹⁸ Thus, it matters *when* the award is drafted. Depending on the duration and complexity of the arbitration, however, it seems unlikely that someone could recall all the relevant facts, disputed facts and party positions off the top of their head. Indeed, the fleeting nature of human recollection is cited to impact both the accuracy and efficiency of the award. For this reason, some authors argue that the drafting process should be started as early as possible.¹⁹⁹ Transcripts could mitigate human forgetfulness too, however, and it is debatable whether this is part of the drafting process. More research is needed to determine the exact scope of what can be considered the drafting of an award. Additionally, thought must be

¹⁹⁰ Peters (n 95), p. 155.

¹⁹¹ *ibid*, p. 155.

¹⁹² Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 200-202; Dasser and Igbokwe (n 75), p. 291-292.

¹⁹³ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 203; Dasser and Igbokwe (n 75), p. 282-283.

¹⁹⁴ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 204; Dasser and Igbokwe (n 75), p. 292.

¹⁹⁵ Elliott Geisinger, 'Presidents Message: Drafting an Award: For Whom? Why?' (2014) 32 ASA Bulletin 683.

¹⁹⁶ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 204-207; Waincymer, *Procedure and Evidence in International Arbitration* (n 77), p. 445-446.

¹⁹⁷ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 204-207.

¹⁹⁸ Peters (n 95), p. 148.

¹⁹⁹ Dasser and Igbokwe (n 75), p. 290; Lorenzo C Martinez IV, 'What Really Matters When an Arbitration Award Is Made' (*Kluwer Arbitration Blog*, 14 February 2021)

<<https://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2021/02/14/what-really-matters-when-an-arbitration-award-is-made/>> accessed 22 May 2024.

given to *how* the award is drafted. When a tribunal secretary is tasked with providing a summary of the party positions, how much discretion does he actually possess? The very essence of summarising requires one to have data and subsequently choose which parts of that data should be left in and which parts should be left out. Is the tribunal secretary simply writing down all the arguments submitted by the parties, or does he only write down what he deems relevant to the case? Does he write them down in a neutral way, or does he place emphasis on matters he considers deserve emphasis the most? Furthermore, thought must be given to how such summaries are used. How much do the arbitrators revisit or rely on summaries? Exactly how much discretion relating to the actual decision-making is delegated away by delegating the drafting of an award? Naturally, this also has to do with how much supervision the tribunal exercises over the tribunal secretary and how much the tribunal secretary influences the arbitral decision-making process. A case of great value in that context is the *P v Q* case, where the Claimant alleged that (members of) the tribunal breached the *intuitu personae* principle in a challenge procedure.²⁰⁰ The claim was based on a misdirected email and an analysis of the time spent by the secretary and the arbitrators.²⁰¹ One of the arbitrators had accidentally sent an email that was meant for the tribunal secretary to one of the parties.²⁰² In this email, the arbitrator sent a draft of a procedural decision and asked the tribunal secretary for his views on it.²⁰³ The argument of the time spent was the same as in the *Yukos* case: an allegedly disproportionate time spent by the tribunal secretary as opposed to the time spent by the arbitrators. This would be proof of the improper delegation of functions to the secretary. The English court rejected the claims. First, the court gave its own definition of the personal and non-delegable arbitral decision-making function, namely:

That function requires each member of the tribunal to bring his own personal and independent judgment to bear on the decision in question, taking account of the rival submissions of the parties; and to exercise reasonable diligence in going about discharging that function. What is required in practice will vary infinitely with the nature of the decision and the circumstances of each case.²⁰⁴

While the court did recognise that decision-making is often a continuous process, the court came to a different conclusion than Jensen did.²⁰⁵ Indeed, the court stated that ‘an arbitrator who receives the views of a tribunal secretary does not thereby necessarily lose the ability to exercise full and independent judgement on the issue in question’.²⁰⁶ Still, the court did acknowledge that a real danger of inappropriate influence over the decision-making process by the tribunal may arise, if the secretary is tasked with anything that involves expressing a

²⁰⁰ *P v Q*, *P v Q* and ors [2017] EWHC 194 (Comm) (High Court, England).

²⁰¹ *ibid*, par. 17.

²⁰² *ibid*.

²⁰³ *ibid*, par. 10.

²⁰⁴ *ibid*, par. 65.

²⁰⁵ *ibid*, paras. 67-70; Jensen, *International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 204-211.

²⁰⁶ *P v Q*, *P v Q* and ors [2017] EWHC 194 (Comm) (High Court, England), part. 67.

view on the substantive merits, application or issue.²⁰⁷ With regard to the time spent, the court considered that the time spent by the secretary was not indicative of any inappropriate role on his part. Moreover, the court stated that drafting the relevant procedural background and parties' submissions for the decisions was a proper function of the secretary and would account for the hours spent.²⁰⁸

Circling back to the topic at hand, it must be recalled that the reason why some authors consider the drafting of (parts of) the award to fall within the scope of the *intuitu personae* principle, is because it would influence arbitral decision-making to an extent where the selected arbitrator(s) no longer discharge(s) their decision-making function sufficiently. The *P v Q* judgment shows that while it may not be best practice to solicit or receive 'any views of any kind' on the substance from a tribunal secretary, it is not a breach of the *intuitu personae* principle. This further synergises with the *Yukos* judgment, the Dutch court stated that a tribunal secretary drafting the text of an arbitral award does not mean that the secretary participated in the decision-making process. Per the court, the choice of the tribunal to use these texts in the award does not amount to a (sufficiently serious) breach of the *intuitu personae* principle, even if the text remains unedited.²⁰⁹ This makes it all the more likely that the drafting of an award by a tribunal secretary on its own does not influence arbitral decision-making to an extent that the *intuitu personae* principle would be breached. At the same time, it would be logical that the drafting of an award could still amount to such a breach, depending on *when* and *how* an award is drafted in relation to the arbitral decision-making process. Indeed, it could be the previously raised questions within the *when* and *how* an award is drafted, that could lead to the tribunal secretary influencing the arbitral decision-making to an unacceptable extent.

§3.7: Arbitration rules on delegating the drafting of an award

As noted in paragraph 3.1, parties can choose to arbitrate before a dispute arises and after a dispute arises. Parties that want to arbitrate have, to a large extent, the right to choose *how* they want to arbitrate. Moreover, arbitrations without the involvement of an arbitral institution are called '*ad hoc*' arbitrations. Parties to *ad hoc* arbitrations can choose to design their arbitration from scratch, allowing the parties to tailor the whole arbitration to their needs and wants.²¹⁰ An effective and efficient tailor-made design, however, requires cooperation between the parties and experience in arbitration.²¹¹ Therefore, parties to *ad hoc* arbitrations commonly choose the predesigned ruleset developed by the United Nations Commission on

²⁰⁷ *ibid*, par. 68.

²⁰⁸ *ibid*, par. 70.

²⁰⁹ *Yukos*, District Court of The Hague 18 February 2020, ECLI:NL:GHDHA:2020:234 (Judgment on appeal, the Netherlands), par. 6.6.14.1.

²¹⁰ Blackaby and others (n 70), paras. 1.140-1.156.

²¹¹ *ibid*.

International Trade Law (UNCITRAL), the ‘UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules’.²¹² Alternatively, parties can choose to have their arbitration conducted under the auspices of an arbitral institution.²¹³ Arbitral institutions are permanent bodies that provide support to arbitrations, such as providing staff, hearing rooms and more. Importantly, arbitral institutions usually have their own tried-and-tested arbitration rules that they administer to the arbitration, unless parties expressly decide otherwise. Parties can modify these rules to the extent that the arbitral institution allows them.²¹⁴ The added convenience that arbitral institutions offer makes it a popular choice for users of arbitration.²¹⁵ It follows that arbitral institutions wield a considerable influence over the field of international arbitration as a whole.²¹⁶ This highlights the importance of examining what the arbitration rules of the leading arbitral institutions say when it comes to the extent to which tribunals can use LLMs to help draft awards. As there are no arbitration rules regarding the use of LLMs yet, value can be had by examining general provisions in arbitration rules that relate to delegating the drafting of an award. Naturally, such delegation often relates to tribunal secretaries.²¹⁷ In that context, the arbitration rules of the leading arbitral institutions often address similar ‘subtopics’, for example the tasks that a tribunal secretary is allowed to carry out.²¹⁸ There are many leading arbitral institutions in international commercial arbitration, as the amount of arbitrations administered by arbitral institutions is rather fractured.²¹⁹ Therefore, this paragraph will limit itself to the top five institutions, namely: the China International Economic and Trade Arbitration Commission (hereafter: CIETAC), the American Arbitration Association’s International Centre for Dispute Resolution (hereafter: ICDR), the International Chamber of Commerce (hereafter: ICC), the Singapore International Arbitration Centre (hereafter: SIAC) and the London Court of International Arbitration (hereafter: LCIA).²²⁰ With regard to international investment arbitration, the majority of known arbitrations are administered by the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (hereafter: ICSID).²²¹ As this

²¹² The UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules are often chosen because it is a ruleset that does not contain any provisions that designate a specific arbitral institution to carry out certain tasks. When a provision designates a specific arbitral institution to carry out a task, but the arbitration is not conducted under the auspices of that institution, then the provision cannot be applied and loses its effects. This makes the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules so attractive in *ad hoc* arbitrations. See to that effect: Blackaby and others (n 70), paras. 1.146-1.181; Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 33-36.

²¹³ Blackaby and others (n 70), paras. 1.140-1.181; Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 15-16.

²¹⁴ Blackaby and others (n 70), paras. 1.146-1.181; Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 33-36.

²¹⁵ Blackaby and others (n 70), para. 1.157.

²¹⁶ Cole and Ortolani (n 52), p. 16.

²¹⁷ Filip De Ly, ‘Rules and Case Law on Tribunal Secretaries’ in Luc Demeyere and Filip De Ly (eds), *Arbitral Secretaries* (Wolters Kluwer 2017); Simon Maynard, ‘Laying the Fourth Arbitrator to Rest: Re-Evaluating the Regulation of Arbitral Secretaries’ (2018) 34 *Arbitration International* 173.

²¹⁸ This will become apparent as the paragraph progresses.

²¹⁹ ‘The ICSID Caseload - Statistics | ICSID’

<<https://icsid.worldbank.org/resources/publications/icsid-caseload-statistics>> accessed 28 May 2024; Roberto Echanti, ‘1. Bilateral Investment Treaties and Investment Provisions in Preferential Trade Agreements: Recent Developments in Investment Rule-Making’ in Katia Yannaca-Small (ed), *Arbitration under international investment agreements: a guide to the key issues* (Second edition, Oxford University Press 2018), p. 4.

²²⁰ Born, *International Commercial Arbitration* (n 110), par. 1.03 (Kluwer Law International, Updated November 2023). Note that the London Maritime Arbitrators Association (LMAA) is not included, as the LMAA exclusively relates to maritime disputes and is technically not an arbitral institution.

²²¹ ICSID Caseload (n 219); Echanti (n 219), p. 4.

makes the ICSID by far the most authoritative arbitral institution in international investment arbitration, this paragraph will not cover other arbitral institutions in that field.²²²

The first subtopic addresses the framework of relevant rules from the aforementioned arbitral institutions. It should be mentioned, however, that the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules are used in both international investment arbitration and international commercial arbitration and can in principle be administered by any arbitral institution.²²³ UNCITRAL has published non-binding guidance notes to guide arbitrators in organising arbitral proceedings. These notes are aptly named ‘Notes on Organizing Arbitral Proceedings’ (hereafter: UNCITRAL Notes).²²⁴ Any arbitration under the ICSID Convention is administered by the Centre.²²⁵ Additionally, arbitrations under the ICSID Convention are by default conducted in accordance with the ICSID Arbitration Rules, unless parties agree otherwise.²²⁶ A common alternative choice is the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules.²²⁷ The ICSID Administrative and Financial Regulations (hereafter: ICSID Regulations) applies to all the arbitrations conducted by the Centre.²²⁸ The CIETAC Arbitration Rules 2024 are applicable to any arbitration administered by the CIETAC, unless parties agree otherwise.²²⁹ The CIETAC also has ‘Guidelines on Evidence’, the application of which is subject to the consent of the parties.²³⁰ The AAA-ICDR International Arbitration Rules 2021 (hereafter: ICDR Rules) are applicable when parties have agreed to arbitrate under these Rules, or when parties have provided for arbitration of an international dispute by either the ICDR, the international division of the AAA or the AAA itself without selecting any particular rules.²³¹ Unless the parties agree otherwise in writing, the ICDR Arbitral Tribunal Secretary Guidelines 2022 (hereafter: ICDR Secretary Guidelines) apply to all cases administered by the ICDR, and may be adopted at the discretion of the tribunal and upon the agreement of the parties in any other cases.²³² The ICC Rules of Arbitration 2021 (hereafter: ICC Rules) apply to all arbitrations administered by the ICC.²³³ In addition to the ICC Rules, there is also a ‘Note to Parties and Arbitral Tribunals on

²²² *ibid.*

²²³ Katia Yannaca-Small and Ucheora Onwuamaegbu (eds), ‘3. International Investment Dispute Settlement Mechanisms’, *Arbitration under international investment agreements: a guide to the key issues* (Second edition, Oxford University Press 2018), p. 58-59.

²²⁴ ‘UNCITRAL Notes on Organizing Arbitral Proceedings (2016) | United Nations Commission On International Trade Law’

<https://uncitral.un.org/en/texts/arbitration/explanatorytexts/organizing_arbitral_proceedings> accessed 29 May 2024.

²²⁵ Born, *International Commercial Arbitration* (n 110), p. 493-507; Articles 1 and 25 ICSID Convention. The Centre may also administer arbitrations that do not satisfy the jurisdictional requirements of the ICSID Convention by way of the Additional Facility Rules, pursuant to those Additional Facility Rules. Given the restraints in time and size of this thesis, arbitrations under the Additional Facility Rules must be excluded from the scope of this paper. Yannaca-Small and Onwuamaegbu (n 223), p. 60.

²²⁶ See to that effect: Article 44 ICSID Convention.

²²⁷ Born, *International Commercial Arbitration* (n 110), p. 520.

²²⁸ Introductory note ICSID Regulations; Yannaca-Small and Onwuamaegbu (n 223), p. 60.

²²⁹ Article 4 CIETAC Arbitration Rules 2024.

²³⁰ ‘Guidelines on Evidence’ (CIETAC) <<https://www.cietac-eu.org/guidelines-on-evidence/>> accessed 29 May 2024.

²³¹ Article 1(1) and (3) ICDR International Arbitration Rules 2021.

²³² Introduction of the ICDR Arbitral Tribunal Secretary Guidelines 2022. See also Article 17 ICDR Rules that suggest that the guidelines are binding if applicable.

²³³ Article 1(2) and 6(1) of the ICC Rules of Arbitration 2021.

the Conduct of Arbitration 2021’ (hereafter: ICC Note), which applies to all arbitrations administered by the ICC, but is not binding.²³⁴ The SIAC Arbitration Rules 2016 (hereafter: SIAC Rules) apply to all arbitrations administered by the SIAC.²³⁵ Furthermore, the SIAC also has a ‘Practice Note for Administered Cases - On the Appointment of Administrative Secretaries 2015’ (hereafter: SIAC Note), which governs the appointment of administrative secretaries by arbitral tribunals in all cases administered by the SIAC.²³⁶ The SIAC Note is binding.²³⁷ Finally, the LCIA Arbitration Rules 2020 (hereafter: LCIA Rules) apply to any arbitration administered by the LCIA.²³⁸ Complementary to the LCIA Rules, there is a non-binding guidance note called the ‘LCIA Guidance Note for Parties and Arbitrators 2020’ (hereafter: LCIA Note).²³⁹ It deserves to be repeated that the ICC Note, the LCIA Note and the UNCITRAL Notes lack a binding effect, as opposed to the binding character of the other rules, notes and guidelines in this framework, provided the consent of the parties is given where necessary. While it would be impractical to keep repeating this throughout the paragraph, it will be reflected on at this paragraph’s end.

With the relevant framework out of the way, it is now time to discuss the second subtopic: the extent to which the appointment of tribunal secretaries is provided. The most ‘extreme’ of the group is the ICSID, as the ICSID Regulations provide a mandatory appointment of a tribunal secretary for each tribunal.²⁴⁰ Less ‘extreme’ are the ICDR, the ICC, the SIAC and the LCIA. All four institutions require prior consent of the parties before appointing a tribunal secretary.²⁴¹ Additionally, these institutions require the tribunal to provide the parties with the tasks that may be carried out by the secretary and the secretary’s *curriculum vitae*, prior to the secretary’s appointment.²⁴² Furthermore, the ICC, the LCIA and the SIAC require the tribunal to submit a declaration of independence and impartiality of the proposed secretary.²⁴³ The UNCITRAL Notes state that tribunals ‘normally disclose’ their wish to appoint a secretary, if it arises, along with the identity of the proposed secretary, the nature of the tasks to be performed by the secretary and the amount and source of the remuneration.²⁴⁴ Lastly, the CIETAC Rules and Guidelines do not mention the appointment of tribunal secretaries at all, nor do they prohibit it. From this subtopic, one can conclude that the use of LLMs in the form of a tribunal secretary could face significant obstacles. Besides obtaining the consent of the

²³⁴ See to that effect: Point 1-2 ICC Note.

²³⁵ Article 1(1) and (2) of the SIAC Arbitration Rules 2016.

²³⁶ Point 1 of the SIAC Practice Note for Administered Cases – On the Appointment of Administrative Secretaries 2015.

²³⁷ Points 1 and 8 SIAC Note.

²³⁸ Preamble of the LCIA Arbitration Rules 2020.

²³⁹ Points 1-5 of the LCIA Guidance Note for Parties and Arbitrators 2020.

²⁴⁰ Regulation 28 ICSID Regulations 2022; Regulation 25 ICSID Regulations 2006.

²⁴¹ Article 17 ICDR International Arbitration Rules 2021; Point 220-221 ICC Note; Point 3 SIAC Note; Article 14.10 LCIA Rules.

²⁴² Articles 14.8 and 14.9-14.10 LCIA Rules; Note 204 LCIA Note; Article 17 ICDR Rules; Point 220-221 ICC Note.

²⁴³ Article 14.9 LCIA Rules 2020; Point 4 SIAC Note; Point 220 of the ICC Note to Parties and Arbitral Tribunals on the Conduct of Arbitration 2021. It should be noted that the ICC goes even further, requiring the tribunal to also submit an undertaking of the tribunal secretary to act in accordance with the ICC Note, and an undertaking of the tribunal to ensure that the tribunal secretary’s undertaking is complied with.

²⁴⁴ Paragraph 38 UNCITRAL Notes on Organizing Arbitral Proceedings (2016).

parties, it would be complicated to establish whether an LLM can be independent and impartial, and whether an LLM can declare itself to be so. More research should be done on that topic. Additionally, it would be strange to have an LLM create its own *curriculum vitae*.

The third subtopic is which tasks the tribunal secretary is allowed to carry out within the framework set out in this paragraph. It should be remarked from the outset that the rules, guidelines and notes of all but the ICSID have stayed largely the same across recent versions. Indeed, changes between the 2006 and 2022 versions show that tribunal secretaries have been given a greater role in arbitrations under the ICSID Rules and ICSID Regulations. The ICSID Regulations from 2006 specifically allowed the tribunal secretary to keep summary minutes of hearings and the performance of other functions relating to the arbitration at the request of the tribunal or at the direction of the Secretary-General.²⁴⁵ The ICSID Regulations from 2022, however, allow the secretary to perform all functions assigned to the Secretary-General by the Regulations, Rules applicable or by the ICSID Convention, provided that the Secretary-General has delegated it to the tribunal secretary.²⁴⁶ Yet, none of those documents assign the function to draft or help draft an award to the Secretary-General. The same provision does provide for the tribunal secretary to assist the parties and the tribunal with the proceeding.²⁴⁷ It is unclear whether that could involve helping to draft an award, as ‘assisting’ is not explained any further. Moving on to the rest of the framework, the SIAC and the CIETAC do not describe which tasks the tribunal secretary is allowed to perform. The ICDR Secretary Guidelines, and the LCIA Rules for that matter, provide that the tribunal secretary has no decision-making authority and must work under the supervision of the arbitral tribunal.²⁴⁸ The LCIA Note is careful to not out-right endorse any particular task for the tribunal secretary as appropriate, but does allow for tribunal secretaries to carry out substantive tasks, such as summarising submissions, preparing first drafts of awards, or sections of awards, provided that the LCIA Rules are complied with.²⁴⁹ Furthermore, the ICDR Secretary Guidelines allow the tribunal secretary to carry out legal research, make summaries, or draft parts of the award, namely the factual or procedural histories, summaries of the parties’ position and procedural orders.²⁵⁰ Similar provisions are provided by the UNCITRAL Notes and the ICC Notes, with the exception that the ICC Notes explicitly require the tribunal to review the work of the secretaries.²⁵¹ It should be noted that there are two important parts of the award that the ICDR Secretary Guidelines, UNCITRAL Notes and ICC Notes did not mention. Indeed, recalling the typical structure of an award as noted in paragraph 3.6, those two parts are the decision and the reasoning of the award. It could be inferred that the decision and reasoning of the award were not mentioned, because of the consideration that the decision and the reasoning of the award are part of arbitral

²⁴⁵ Regulation 25(c) and (d) of the ICSID Administrative and Financial Regulations 2006, adopted pursuant to Article 6(1)(a) ICSID Convention.

²⁴⁶ Regulation 28(a) ICSID Regulations 2022.

²⁴⁷ Regulation 28(b) ICSID Regulations 2022.

²⁴⁸ Guideline ‘d’ and ‘e’ ICDR Arbitral Tribunal Secretary Guidelines 2022; Article 14.8 LCIA Rules.

²⁴⁹ Point 201-202 LCIA Note.

²⁵⁰ Guideline ‘e’ of the ICDR Arbitral Tribunal Secretary Guidelines 2022.

²⁵¹ Point 220-225 ICC Note; Paragraph 35 UNCITRAL Notes.

decision-making. This would be supported by the fact that the aforementioned documents stress that tribunal secretaries do not possess any decision-making authority and must work under supervision of the tribunal. Admittedly, the aforementioned documents did not provide exhaustive lists of permissible tasks, which means that the drafting of the decision or reasoning of an award could be permissible regardless.²⁵² Furthermore, it should be noted that the ICC Notes and the UNCITRAL Notes are not binding, which further diminishes the argument. In the light of the foregoing, it must be concluded that the examined framework in this paragraph does not signify a broad consensus on whether the drafting of a decision and reasoning of an award may be delegated.²⁵³

All in all, the examined framework shows that the appointment of a tribunal secretary generally requires prior consent of the parties. Additionally, tribunal secretaries are generally judged on their person, not only when it comes to their *curriculum vitae*, but also when it comes to their impartiality and independence. With regard to tasks, there seems to be some consensus for tribunal secretaries to carry out legal research, provide summaries and draft certain parts of the award. Whether that extends to drafting the decision and reasoning of the award too, remains to be seen.

§3.8: The comparability of LLMs and tribunal secretaries

The recent development of LLMs makes it hard to establish whether the *intuitu personae* principle prohibits arbitral tribunals from using an LLM to help draft an award. Indeed, the developments of LLMs have outpaced existing literature, arbitration rules and case law on this particular question. Therefore, paragraph 3.2 drew a preliminary comparison between the role of a tribunal secretary and an LLM. Indeed, if the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit the delegation of assisting in the draft of an award to *someone* else, would the *intuitu personae* principle not prohibit such delegation to *something* else? Paragraph 3.2 stated that to determine whether this comparison holds any merit, it had to be determined whether the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit the delegation of assisting in the draft of an award to *someone* else in the first place. Subsequently, there had to be an understanding of the reasons behind the outcome of the aforementioned. This was accomplished in the previous paragraphs. To briefly summarise, the *intuitu personae* principle was considered to entail that there are certain specific tasks in the arbitrator's mandate that are so interwoven with the identity of the arbitrator, that the delegation of such tasks would contravene the very act of selecting the arbitrator. The *intuitu personae* principle would therefore prohibit arbitrators from delegating their personal mandate to someone else. It was found that the reason why some authors consider the drafting of (parts of) the award to fall within the scope of the

²⁵² If one considers drafting the decision or the reasons of an award to be an essential duty of an arbitrator, then this would be less likely regarding the ICC Note. The ICC Note states that the tribunal may not rely on a tribunal secretary to perform on its behalf any of the essential duties of an arbitrator. See to that effect: Point 223 ICC Note; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 204-207.

²⁵³ See to that effect also: Sophia Elisabeth von Dewall, 'Tribunal Secretaries: How to Prevent a Friend from Turning into a Foe?' in Filip De Ly and Luc Demeyere (eds), *Arbitral secretaries: reports from the joint NAI-CEPANI colloquium, October 5, 2017* (Wolters Kluwer 2018).

intuitu personae principle, is because it would influence arbitral decision-making to an extent where the selected arbitrator(s) no longer discharge(s) their decision-making function sufficiently. The arbitration rules examined in paragraph 3.7 would suggest that some arbitral institutions share that view. Judgments from the *Yukos* case and the *P v Q* case, however, would suggest that the drafting of an award by itself does not influence arbitral decision-making to an extent that the *intuitu personae* principle would be breached. At the same time, it would be logical that the drafting of an award could still amount to such a breach, depending on *when* and *how* an award is drafted in relation to the arbitral decision-making process. Indeed, it could be the previously raised questions within the *when* and *how* an award is drafted, that could lead to the tribunal secretary influencing the arbitral decision-making to an unacceptable extent. While there was no conclusive answer to whether the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit the delegation of assisting in the draft of an award to *someone* else, the previous paragraphs did provide an indication as to how the *intuitu personae* principle could prohibit the delegation of drafting an award to tribunal secretaries. But does the *intuitu personae* principle apply in the same way to LLMs?

Based on the findings in the previous paragraphs, that question essentially boils down to whether an LLM drafting an award could lead to the LLM influencing the arbitral decision-making to an unacceptable extent. At first glance, it may appear obvious that such a situation could occur. Indeed, many questions raised in paragraph 3.6 would equally apply to LLMs. When one starts to compare LLMs with other tools and materials, however, it becomes more complicated. Would reading a book on a certain topic be considered being influenced to an unacceptable extent? If an arbitrator asking his secretary for his opinion does not constitute enough of an influence on the arbitrator's decision-making to be considered a breach of the *intuitu personae* principle, then why would the responses of an LLM be considered problematic? Especially if you consider the common view that an LLM is just a mindless regurgitator of existing data that by virtue of fancy statistics amalgamates some related words back to you.²⁵⁴ How would an LLM compare to a specialised search engine that provides an arbitrator with certain information that changes the arbitrator's view on the case, resulting in a different decision? In that context, it should be noted that LLMs are clearly more than just glorified calculators. As mentioned in chapter 2, LLMs are capable of generating new data from existing data. When zero-shot models are prompted to perform a task they have never seen examples of, they will attempt to apply the learned concepts in order to perform the new task.²⁵⁵ While it is currently unclear whether LLMs can actually

²⁵⁴ Emily M Bender and others, 'On the Dangers of Stochastic Parrots: Can Language Models Be Too Big?', *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency* (ACM 2021) <<https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3442188.3445922>> accessed 14 February 2024, p. 611; Steven T Piantadosi and Felix Hill, 'Meaning without Reference in Large Language Models' (2022) abs/2208.02957 ArXiv <<https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:251371595>> ; Jacob Browning, "'Personhood and AI: Why Large Language Models Don't Understand Us'" [2023] AI & SOCIETY <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01724-y>>.

²⁵⁵ 'What Is Zero-Shot Learning? | IBM' (11 April 2024) <<https://www.ibm.com/topics/zero-shot-learning>> accessed 6 May 2024.

understand human language,²⁵⁶ the author of this paper believes that LLMs compare more to tribunal secretaries than to calculators. Indeed, you will get a better result instructing an LLM to draft an award than you will get from instructing a calculator to do so.

Aside from potentially not being capable of understanding human language, there is another glaring difference between LLMs and tribunal secretaries: LLMs lack legal personhood.²⁵⁷ Even though an AI-robot has been given legal personhood before, it is unlikely that LLMs will be given legal personhood in any meaningful capacity in the near future.²⁵⁸ Consequently, LLMs lack the legal capacity to sign contracts. Therefore, any obligation can only be derived from a contract with the publisher or developer of the LLM. This could lead to unforeseen consequences. For example, the lack of personhood can lead to strange interactions with the arbitration rules from arbitral institutions. Rule 34(3) of the ICSID Rules states that the tribunal may be assisted by the tribunal secretary in its deliberations and that no other person shall assist the tribunal, unless the tribunal decides otherwise and notifies the parties beforehand. The same goes for the LCIA Rules, where only the tribunal secretary is allowed to be privy to the deliberations of the tribunal.²⁵⁹ Would that mean that arbitrators cannot use an LLM under those rules?

Another difference between LLMs and tribunal secretaries, is that tribunal secretaries can be ambitious, which can lead to the unprompted sharing of views.²⁶⁰ Indeed, many tribunal secretaries are new professionals that are under ‘apprenticeship’ by an arbitrator. By ‘learning-by-doing’, there is a greater chance of the tribunal secretary influencing an arbitrator to an unacceptable extent.²⁶¹ While LLMs do not always follow instructions correctly, LLMs are currently incapable of operating autonomously and thus do not pose that risk.

All in all, it can be concluded that in the light of the *intuitu personae* principle, LLMs share more characteristics with tribunal secretaries than with calculators. Therefore, the preliminary comparison from paragraph 3.2 was warranted.

²⁵⁶ Piantadosi and Hill (n 255); Yupeng Chang and others, ‘A Survey on Evaluation of Large Language Models’ (2024) 15 ACM Trans. Intell. Syst. Technol. <<https://doi.org/10.1145/3641289>>, p. 4-5.

²⁵⁷ Lawrence B Solum, ‘Legal Personhood for Artificial Intelligences’, *Machine ethics and robot ethics* (Routledge 2020); Browning (n 254).

²⁵⁸ Solum (n 257); Browning (n 254); Zara Stone, ‘Everything You Need To Know About Sophia, The World’s First Robot Citizen’ (*Forbes*) <<https://www.forbes.com/sites/zarastone/2017/11/07/everything-you-need-to-know-about-sophia-the-worlds-first-robot-citizen/>> accessed 16 May 2024;

²⁵⁹ Article 30.2 LCIA Rules; Point 218 LCIA Note.

²⁶⁰ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 70), p. 63-68.

²⁶¹ *ibid.*

§3.9: Conclusion

This chapter has examined potential party autonomy-related risks and challenges that may arise when an arbitral tribunal uses an LLM to help draft an arbitral award. Party autonomy refers to the principle that parties are free to design their own arbitration procedures to tailor to their particular needs and preferences. Party autonomy therefore takes a central role in international arbitration. Arguably the most important choice that the parties can make, is selecting the arbitrators. It is that selection that gives rise to the *intuitu personae* principle, which entails that there are certain specific tasks in the arbitrator's mandate that are so interwoven with the identity of the arbitrator, that the delegation of such tasks would contravene the very act of selecting the arbitrator. The *intuitu personae* principle would therefore prohibit arbitrators from delegating their personal mandate to someone else. This raised the question whether the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit an arbitral tribunal from using an LLM to help draft an award. As there was no case law or literature to answer that question, a preliminary comparison was drawn between LLMs and tribunal secretaries. Thus, it was researched whether the *intuitu personae* principle would prohibit an arbitral tribunal from using a tribunal secretary to help draft an award. Further research regarding the personal mandate of the arbitrator revealed that arbitral decision-making falls within the scope of the *intuitu personae* principle. In the literature, some authors considered that a tribunal delegating the drafting of parts of an award to a tribunal secretary would influence arbitral decision-making to the extent that the selected arbitrator no longer discharges their decision-making function sufficiently, particularly the decision itself and the reasoning of the award. The consequence of that would be the *intuitu personae* principle prohibiting the delegation of drafting those parts of the award. It was found that such a risk would only potentially present itself if the parties did not consent to such delegation. Analysis of the judgments from the *Yukos* case and the *P v Q* case, suggested that the drafting of an award by itself does not influence arbitral decision-making to an extent that the *intuitu personae* principle would be breached. It was proposed that the tribunal secretary could still influence the arbitral decision-making to an unacceptable extent, however, depending on *when* and *how* an award is drafted in relation to the arbitral decision-making process. It was found that the leading arbitral institutions lacked a unison stance on whether the drafting of a decision and reasoning of an award may be delegated. There was, however, some consensus found on the appointment of tribunal secretaries. Most arbitral institutions require prior consent of the parties. Additionally, tribunal secretaries are generally judged on their person, not only when it comes to their *curriculum vitae*, but also when it comes to their impartiality and independence. With regard to tasks, there seems to be some consensus for tribunal secretaries to carry out legal research, provide summaries and draft certain parts of the award. Finally, the preliminary comparison between LLMs and tribunal secretaries was revisited. It was found that this comparison was warranted, as many of the reasons why tribunal secretaries could influence arbitral decision-making to an unacceptable extent would apply to LLMs as well.

Chapter 4: Large Language Models and Confidentiality

§4.1: Introduction

This chapter explores the potential confidentiality-related risks and challenges that may arise when an arbitral tribunal uses an LLM to help draft an award. This paragraph introduces the term confidentiality and provides some preliminary remarks on the matter. Paragraph 4.2 examines how an obligation of confidentiality could impact the extent to which an arbitral tribunal can use an LLM to help draft an award. Paragraph 4.3 discusses how confidentiality could impact the availability of data to use for training LLMs. Paragraph 4.4 draws a conclusion.

In the context of international arbitration, the term ‘confidentiality’ can be defined as the principle or obligation to not disclose matters within its scope to a third party.²⁶² This obligation can be derived from the parties’ agreement, the applicable arbitration rules and *lex arbitri*.²⁶³ As follows from paragraph 3.1, parties are able to choose the seat, select which arbitration rules are applicable and design the party agreement. In absence of the parties’ agreement, however, there will still be an arbitral seat.²⁶⁴ The law of that seat could introduce a confidentiality obligation too. Therefore, the scope and existence of this obligation is not exclusively, but principally determined by party autonomy.²⁶⁵ While the scope can thus vary, it is common that it includes any matters arising from or disclosed during an arbitration.²⁶⁶ In the absence of any reference to confidentiality in the party agreement, arbitration rules or *lex arbitri*, however, the point of departure is the absence of confidentiality itself.²⁶⁷ While the default mode may be the absence of confidentiality, most arbitrations are confidential.²⁶⁸ While some authors credit the ease with which confidentiality is implemented to explain why most arbitrations are confidential, others credit the advantages that confidentiality has to offer.²⁶⁹ In fact, some authors consider confidentiality a ‘key selling point’ of international arbitration.²⁷⁰ In contrast to public litigation, parties do not need to worry about submitting commercially-sensitive data to support their arguments. Furthermore, confidentiality would

²⁶² Robert Argen, ‘Ending Blind Spot Justice: Broadening the Transparency Trend in International Arbitration’ (2014) 40 Brooklyn Journal of International Law, p. 214-215; Katie Chung and others, ‘Practical Insights on Confidentiality’, p. 1.

²⁶³ Katie Chung and others, ‘Practical Insights on Confidentiality’, p. 1.

²⁶⁴ Tony Cole and Pietro Ortolani, *Understanding International Arbitration* (2020), p. 29-30.

²⁶⁵ J Ole Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (First edition, Oxford University Press 2019), 204.

²⁶⁶ Chung and others (n 263), p. 1.

²⁶⁷ Argen (n 262), p. 215-216; Chung and others (n 263), p. 1.

²⁶⁸ Cole and Ortolani (n 264), p. 124.

²⁶⁹ Argen (n 262), p. 216-217; Sherlin Tung and Brian Lin, ‘More Transparency in International Commercial Arbitration: To Have or Not to Have?’ (31 May 2018) <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3188001>> accessed 27 October 2023; Jane Parsons, ‘Publish and Be Damned: Should We Embrace the Systematic Publication of Arbitral Awards?’ (*Arbitration Blog*, 27 February 2017) <<http://arbitrationblog.practicallaw.com/publish-and-be-damned-should-we-embrace-the-systematic-publication-of-arbitral-awards/>> accessed 27 October 2023.

²⁷⁰ Tung and Lin (n 269); Parsons (n 269).

allow the parties to escape scrutiny from its customers, peers and competitors alike.²⁷¹ Not everyone, however, considers confidentiality to be advantageous in international arbitration. In the past two decades, more and more authors argue that the need for transparency is greater than confidentiality, stating that transparency should be promoted over confidentiality.²⁷² While the former position retains its dominance in international commercial arbitration, the latter position is trending more and more in international investment arbitration.²⁷³ This is unsurprising, as international investment arbitration disputes can potentially generate great public interest and far-reaching policy implications.²⁷⁴ Consequently, those in favour of transparency consider it problematic to drape such disputes under the ‘stifling cloak of confidentiality’, essentially depriving the general public of this information.²⁷⁵ While a convincing argument can be made that disputes involving matters of public interest can also occur in international commercial arbitration, the call for transparency there has gone largely unanswered.²⁷⁶ This has led to some divergences between international commercial arbitration and international investment arbitration.²⁷⁷ Absent matters of public interest, however, the principle of confidentiality largely works the same in both fields.²⁷⁸

§4.2: Confidentiality and the use of LLMs

As outlined in chapter 2, one has to submit a prompt in order to receive output from an LLM. One can construe their prompt in such a way that it maximises the usefulness of the output. This is commonly referred to as ‘prompt engineering’.²⁷⁹ It is important to note that prompts that contain more details yield a more specific and relevant output.²⁸⁰ It follows that in order to use an LLM optimally, the tribunal would need to include extensive details of the arbitration in its prompts. Given the importance of confidentiality in international arbitration and the often sensitive data submitted by the parties, this could be problematic in and of

²⁷¹ Tung and Lin (n 269), p. 24-25.

²⁷² Timothy Foden and Odysseas G Repousis, ‘Giving Away Home Field Advantage: The Misguided Attack on Confidentiality in International Commercial Arbitration’ (2019) 35 *ARBITRATION INTERNATIONAL* 401.

²⁷³ Andrea Menaker and Eckhard R Hellbeck, ‘9. Piercing the Veil of Confidentiality: The Recent Trend towards Greater Public Participation and Transparency in Investment Treaty Arbitration’ in Katia Yannaca-Small (ed), *Arbitration Under International Investment Agreements: A Guide to the Key Issues* (2nd edn, Oxford University Press 2018), p. 183.

²⁷⁴ *ibid.*, p. 183. Consider also the regulatory chilling effect that these disputes can cause. See to that effect: *Philip Morris Asia Limited (Hong Kong) v. The Commonwealth of Australia*, PCA case 2012-12 (Permanent Court of Arbitration, Singapore); *Vattenfall AB and others v. Federal Republic of Germany*, ICSID Case No. ARB/12/12 (ICSID, Germany).

²⁷⁵ Argen (n 262), p. 230-235; Stefan Pislevik, ‘Precedent and Development of Law: Is It Time for Greater Transparency in International Commercial Arbitration?’ (2018) 34 *Arbitration International* 241, p. 244-246.

²⁷⁶ Argen (n 262), p. 207-213; Tung and Lin (n 269), p. 28.

²⁷⁷ Argen (n 262), p. 245.

²⁷⁸ Emmanuel Jolivet, ‘Access to Information and Awards*’ (2006) 22 *Arbitration International* 265. Richard C Reuben, ‘Confidentiality in Arbitration: Beyond the Myth’ (20 August 2006) <<https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=925281>> accessed 27 October 2023. Argen (n 262); Parsons (n 269); Pislevik (n 275).

²⁷⁹ ‘Hacking the System: Admissibility of Evidence from Cyberattacks in Arbitration’ <<https://globalarbitrationreview.com/review/the-arbitration-review-of-the-americas/2024/article/hacking-the-system-admissibility-of-evidence-cyberattacks-in-arbitration>> accessed 15 May 2024.

²⁸⁰ *ibid.*

itself. Indeed, if a tribunal submits confidential information in a prompt to an LLM, could that submission be considered a disclosure of confidential information to a third party? In order to solve that question, it should be recalled that the existence and scope of confidentiality are principally determined by party autonomy. Therefore, any discussion on this topic will be of general character. The first step towards determining how an obligation of confidentiality could affect the discretion of the tribunal, is to determine to whom such an obligation would typically extend. Much like the definition given in paragraph 4.1 would suggest, the obligation of confidentiality rests on participants of the arbitration.²⁸¹ Indeed, the duty to not disclose to third parties implies that this duty rests on those that are not third parties. Thus, this duty is certainly placed on each individual arbitrator of the arbitral tribunal.²⁸² It must be noted that the question at hand can only arise in situations where party consent has not been provided. Indeed, consider the situation where the tribunal informs the parties of its intention to use an LLM to help draft an award and the parties' consent to this use. In such a case, it would be silly if this use with the parties' consent could breach any typical obligation of confidentiality, given that parties imposed the confidentiality beforehand.²⁸³ Conversely, if parties explicitly state that LLMs are not to be used in the arbitration whatsoever, then this would be grounds for a denial of recognition and enforcement or the setting aside of that award.²⁸⁴ Therefore, the question at hand only has a realistic application to situations where party consent has neither been provided nor withheld.²⁸⁵ Drawing a comparison to tribunal secretaries once again, such situations occur when arbitral tribunals do not disclose the appointment of a tribunal secretary.²⁸⁶ Similarly, such situations could occur when arbitral tribunals do not disclose the use of an LLM. When it comes to the participation of undisclosed secretaries, a distinction is made between 'internal' and 'external' secretaries.²⁸⁷ Internal secretaries exercise their duties in the discharge of their main contractual relationship with the arbitrator or the arbitrator's law firm. Conversely, external secretaries have no pre-existing contractual or factual relationship with any of the arbitrators or institutions.²⁸⁸ With regard to internal secretaries, it is usually the case that their main contractual relationship contains the obligation to keep sensitive work-related matters confidential.²⁸⁹ Those secretaries are deemed to be 'within the sphere of confidence of the arbitrator', which allows the arbitrator to share with them details of the arbitration without breaching the obligation of confidentiality.²⁹⁰ External secretaries and

²⁸¹ Takunda T Gumbu, 'A Behavioural Approach to Confidentiality Rules and Practices in International Arbitration', p. 331.

²⁸² Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 265), p. 150, 164-165.

²⁸³ See for example Articles 24.4 and 39.1-39.3 SIAC Rules.

²⁸⁴ Günther J Horvath, 'The Duty of the Tribunal to Render an Enforceable Award' (2001) 18 *Journal of International Arbitration*, p. 145.

²⁸⁵ See to that effect: Decision of the Swiss Federal Tribunal 4A_709/2014 - 21 May 2015 (Swiss Federal Tribunal, Geneva).

²⁸⁶ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 265), p. 164-165.

²⁸⁷ *ibid*, p. 167-168.

²⁸⁸ *ibid*, p. 94.

²⁸⁹ *ibid*, p. 167-168.

²⁹⁰ *ibid*; Chung and others (n 263), p. 626-627. Alternatively, see: Benjamin F Hughes, 'Chapter 17: The Problem of Undisclosed Assistance to Arbitral Tribunals' in Patricia Shaughnessy, Sherlin Tung and Pierre A

other professional persons assisting in the conduct of the arbitration, however, are not party to such a ‘main contractual relationship’. Therefore, their ‘secrecy’ must be guaranteed by another source.²⁹¹ This could be either professional privilege or a newly drawn up confidentiality agreement between the arbitrator and the external party. Bringing back the discussion to the role of LLMs, could anything of the above apply to LLMs as well?

First and foremost, it should be recalled from paragraph 3.8 that LLMs currently lack legal personhood. Consequently, LLMs lack the legal capacity to sign contracts and confidentiality agreements. Therefore, any obligation of confidentiality or professional privilege can only be derived from a contract with the publisher or developer of the LLM. This allows for three options. Firstly, one could consider a contract between the publisher of an LLM and the law firm of the arbitrator a ‘main contractual relationship’, similar to that of an internal secretary.²⁹² Secondly, one could consider the publisher of the LLM to be an independent provider of business services, who should be bound by professional privilege in the performance of their services to the tribunal.²⁹³ More research is needed to find out whether that is truly the case. The third and final option would require the arbitral tribunal to sign a confidentiality agreement with the publisher of the LLM before use. It could be interesting to research whether the general terms of service of ChatGPT could be construed as such.

In the light of the foregoing, one can conclude that the undisclosed use of an LLM by an arbitral tribunal does not constitute a breach of a typical obligation of confidentiality, provided that a similar obligation of confidentiality rests on the publisher or developer of the LLM.

Following the submission of a prompt that includes confidential information, thought should be given to what happens with the data next. Indeed, it could be extremely problematic if a prompt containing confidential data from the arbitration were to be obtained by an unauthorised party.²⁹⁴ While LLMs have cybersecurity measures in place to prevent unauthorised parties from accessing prompts of others, such security does not always measure up against hackers.²⁹⁵ LLMs like Gemini and ChatGPT store prompts submitted to them in databases, which can and have been breached before.²⁹⁶ Furthermore, LLMs like

Karrer (eds), *The powers and duties of an arbitrator: liber amicorum Pierre A. Karrer* (Kluwer Law International 2017), p. 164.

²⁹¹ Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 265), p. 94; Tung and Lin (n 269), p. 626-627.

²⁹² Consider the extra protection of business data that ChatGPT Enterprise Privacy offers: ‘Enterprise Privacy’ <<https://openai.com/enterprise-privacy/>> accessed 15 May 2024.

²⁹³ Tung and Lin (n 269), p. 627.

²⁹⁴ Ghazal Bhootra and Ishan Puranik, ‘Arbi(Traitor)?: A Case against AI Arbitrators’ (2022) 4 Indian Arbitration Law Review 29, p. 43.

²⁹⁵ David Haber, Elliot Webster and Ads Dawson, ‘Decoding OWASP Large Language Model Security Verification Standard (LLMSVS)’ (9 April 2024) <<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uePk-WalURk>>.

²⁹⁶ ‘Gemini Apps Privacy Hub - Gemini Apps Help’

<https://support.google.com/gemini/answer/13594961?visit_id=638513892932875831-2835953497&p=privacy_help&rd=1#collected_data> accessed 15 May 2024; ‘Enterprise Privacy’

<<https://openai.com/enterprise-privacy/>> accessed 15 May 2024; ‘ChatGPT Confirms Data Breach, Raising Security Concerns’ (*Security Intelligence*)

Gemini reserve the right to use submitted prompts as training data.²⁹⁷ Tribunals thus run the risk that training data, containing their submitted prompt, is ‘prompt hacked’. Prompt hacking or prompt mining is commonly used to describe the act of engineering prompts with the purpose of tricking an LLM into revealing its training data.²⁹⁸ Additionally, network traffic from the user to the servers of the LLM can potentially be intercepted, thus allowing hackers access to the submitted prompts.²⁹⁹ To avoid such problems, tribunals could opt for in-house LLMs.³⁰⁰ This means that the LLMs would only operate on a local network. While this would mitigate some of the cybersecurity vulnerabilities, it does not mitigate them all. Presently, many appliances like coffee machines, water coolers and vending machines are connected to the local networks of the offices that use them.³⁰¹ At the same time, many of these ‘smart’ appliances have little to no security.³⁰² As a result, hackers can breach the security of these smart appliances in order to gain unauthorised access to the local network.³⁰³ All in all, the security of a submitted prompt can never be fully guaranteed.

<<https://securityintelligence.com/articles/chatgpt-confirms-data-breach/securityintelligence.com/articles/chatgpt-confirms-data-breach>> accessed 15 May 2024.

²⁹⁷ Gemini (n 296).

²⁹⁸ ‘Prompt Hacking: The New Cyber Threat’ (*Prompt Engineering*, 5 March 2024)

<<https://promptengineering.org/the-rise-of-a-new-threat-prompt-hacking/>> accessed 15 May 2024.

²⁹⁹ Haber, Webster and Dawson (n 295).

³⁰⁰ ‘Lower Data Breaches and Security Risks with Local Language Models’

<<https://www.netguru.com/blog/lower-data-breaches-and-security-risks-with-local-language-models>> accessed 15 May 2024.

³⁰¹ A. Gai and others, ‘Categorisation of Security Threats for Smart Home Appliances’, *2018 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)* (2018); *ibid.*

³⁰² Gai and others (n 301).

³⁰³ Gai and others (n 301); Netguru (n 300).

§4.3: The training LLMs on awards and confidentiality

As mentioned in chapter 2, LLMs can be trained on performing specific tasks by ‘feeding’ them specific data. While zero-shot LLMs do perform surprisingly well in certain tasks related to the legal field, a well-trained LLM is expected to perform better.³⁰⁴ To develop an LLM specifically to help draft awards, it is therefore prudent to have a large sample size of awards.³⁰⁵ Few awards have been published, however, as confidentiality is rather prevalent in international arbitration.³⁰⁶ In the past two decades, however, more and more authors argue that the need for transparency is greater than the need for confidentiality.³⁰⁷ As a consequence, many awards in investment arbitration are now publicised instead of being kept confidential.³⁰⁸ In international commercial arbitration, however, there is still a strong desire to keep awards confidential.³⁰⁹ Consequently, the lack of publicised awards in international commercial arbitration could prove to be problematic for developers that want to train their LLM on awards. Indeed, the more data to ‘feed’ the LLM, the more accurate it becomes. A lack of ‘feed’ could result in a so-called ‘data diet’, meaning that there is not enough available data to sufficiently train an LLM.³¹⁰ Consequently, any inaccuracies or biases in the available data would not be balanced out by other data. This could lead to a lack of accuracy and an increase in bias in the LLM.³¹¹

There are three solutions to this problem that come to mind. Firstly, developers could hope that the trend towards transparency would continue in international commercial arbitration so that there would eventually be enough data available to train the LLM. This could take years upon years, and it is not guaranteed that this trend of transparency would continue. In an attempt to find the middle ground, an author recently proposed that all arbitral awards should be published, but with the confidential data redacted.³¹² Recalling the reasons why parties choose confidentiality, it would require the redaction of a substantial amount of data in order to safeguard those reasons. It is unlikely that the remaining data would be of much use to the LLM. Secondly, developers could try to train the LLM on other sources than publicised

³⁰⁴ In this context, I refer to attribute-based zero-shot models that apply logic stemming from parts of existing cases to new cases. This is illustrated with the following quote: “*For example, a model can learn “stripes” from images of tigers and zebras; it can learn “yellow” from images of canaries, and “flying insect” from images of flies. The model can now perform zero-shot classification of bees, despite the absence of bee images in the training set, because it can understand them as a combination of learned features: “yellow, striped flying insects.”*”, see to that effect: ‘What Is Zero-Shot Learning? | IBM’ (23 January 2024) <<https://www.ibm.com/topics/zero-shot-learning>> accessed 17 May 2024. See also: Bhootra and Puranik (n 294), p. 41-43.

³⁰⁵ Maxi Scherer, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Legal Decision-Making: The Wide Open?’ [2019] *Journal of International Arbitration* 539, p.554-555.

³⁰⁶ Cole and Ortolani (n 264), p. 124.

³⁰⁷ Foden and Repousis (n 272).

³⁰⁸ Katie Chung and Michael Hwang, ‘Defining the Indefinable: Practical Problems of Confidentiality in Arbitration’ [2009] *Journal of International Arbitration* 609, p. 640.

³⁰⁹ Menaker and Hellbeck (n 272), p. 183.

³¹⁰ Scherer, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Legal Decision-Making’ (n 305), p. 558-560.

³¹¹ Scherer, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Legal Decision-Making’ (n 305), p. 559-560.

³¹² Orlando Federico Cabrera Colorado, ‘The Future of International Arbitration in the Age of Artificial Intelligence’ (2023) 40 *Journal of International Arbitration* 301, p. 338. It should be noted that the ICC already regularly publishes redacted awards, see to that effect: Points 57-64 ICC Notes.

awards. Books, journals, submissions by arbitrators, counsel and professors, it could all help in development. The downside could be the cost, as it becomes more and more apparent that developers need to purchase a licence in order to use copyrighted data to train their LLM.³¹³ Developers would have to negotiate with many different parties, increasing the costs further. Awards themselves, however, do not seem to bear any copyright at first glance, although more research is required. This leads up to the third solution: asking institutions to use their confidential awards in order to train an LLM. This is not too far-fetched, as LLM developers are already asking law firms to use confidential data of their clients to train their LLM.³¹⁴ Astonishingly, these requests are sometimes granted.³¹⁵ While most arbitration institutions require prior consent of both parties to publish a (confidential) award,³¹⁶ this could potentially be circumvented with the promise that the aim is to train an LLM, rather than publication.³¹⁷ Indeed, some authors consider confidentiality to only be breached in the event that the information enters 'public domain'.³¹⁸ Therefore, one could argue that if the training data never enters public domain, it would not be a breach of confidentiality to disclose details of the arbitration to the developer of an LLM. The data in question would supposedly never see the light of day. As mentioned in paragraph 4.2, however, LLMs have been tricked into revealing its training data before. It follows that the use of confidential awards as training data for LLMs does pose a risk to its confidentiality. Consequently, institutions should not forgo obtaining prior permissions of the parties in order to allow the use of their confidential awards as training data for an LLM.

³¹³ Michael M Grynbaum and Ryan Mac, 'The Times Sues OpenAI and Microsoft Over A.I. Use of Copyrighted Work' *The New York Times* (27 December 2023)

<<https://www.nytimes.com/2023/12/27/business/media/new-york-times-open-ai-microsoft-lawsuit.html>> accessed 16 May 2024.

³¹⁴ Lucian T Pera, 'Prudently Training AI on Client Confidential Information' *American Bar* (1 March 2024) <https://www.americanbar.org/groups/law_practice/resources/law-practice-magazine/2024/2024-march-april/prudently-training-ai-on-client-confidential-information/> accessed 16 May 2024.

³¹⁵ *ibid.*

³¹⁶ Parsons (n 269).

³¹⁷ See to that effect: Chung and Hwang (n 308), p. 627; Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (n 265), p. 167-168.

³¹⁸ *ibid.*

§4.4: Conclusion

This chapter has explored the potential confidentiality-related risks and challenges that might emerge when an arbitral tribunal uses an LLM to help draft an award. In the context of international arbitration, the term ‘confidentiality’ was defined as the principle or obligation to not disclose within its scope to a third party. The scope and existence of this obligation was found to be principally determined by party autonomy. To account for the variance inherent to party autonomy, a typical obligation of confidentiality was used for the examination of potential confidentiality-related risks. Two categories of confidentiality-related risks were identified: the submission of confidential information via prompts and the submission of confidential data for training. The first category originates from the fact that in order to use an LLM optimally, the tribunal would need to include extensive details of the arbitration in its prompts. Two potential risks were identified and explored within this category. The first potential risk was whether the submission of a prompt containing confidential information could be considered a disclosure of confidential information to a third party, thereby breaching a typical confidentiality obligation. It was found that where party consent to use an LLM is not provided, nor withheld, the undisclosed use of an LLM by an arbitral tribunal would not constitute a breach of a typical obligation of confidentiality, provided that a similar obligation of confidentiality rests on the publisher or developer of the LLM. The second potential risk was the added risks that emerge when a prompt containing confidential information is submitted to an LLM. It was found that the security of a submitted prompt could never be fully guaranteed. The second category of confidentiality-related risks originates from the fact that in order for an LLM to function optimally, it would need to have vast amounts of unredacted awards as training data. With the lack of publicised unredacted awards established, the use of confidential awards as training data was explored as a possible solution. As LLMs have been ‘tricked’ before into revealing training data, this solution was found to pose a risk to confidentiality.

Chapter 5: Large Language Models and the Award

§5.1: Introduction

This chapter focuses on the risks that may arise regarding the validity, recognition and enforcement of awards drafted with the help of an LLM. First, some preliminary remarks are provided. Paragraph 5.2 discusses the formal requirements for an award. Paragraph 5.3 explores the fourth arbitrator defence and its potential implications for LLMs. Paragraph 5.4 briefly addresses public policy provisions related to LLMs. Paragraph 5.5 will draw a conclusion.

There is no internationally accepted definition of an arbitral ‘award’, as was mentioned in paragraph 3.5. Still, there is consensus to describe arbitral awards as ‘final’ and ‘binding’.³¹⁹ ‘Final’ in the context of the New York Convention means that certain, and not necessarily all, disputed points submitted for arbitration are resolved and concluded.³²⁰ ‘Binding’ means that the award must be complied with by the parties.³²¹ There are also partial awards, which are awards that do not deal with all the outstanding issues but only some or even a single issue.³²² Similarly, there are certain provisional measures that a tribunal can take that can also be categorised as partial awards.³²³ Partial awards that resolve at least a part of the dispute in a final manner are treated the same way as ‘regular’ awards under the New York Convention, provided they can be effectively ‘detached’ from the remaining issues of the dispute.³²⁴ Partial awards, when only pertaining to jurisdiction, are also referred to as ‘jurisdictional awards’.³²⁵ Those awards can qualify for recognition only, as they are exclusively of a declaratory nature.³²⁶ Recently, some arbitral institutions have provided parties with the possibility to obtain a decision from an ‘emergency arbitrator’, prior to the constitution of the arbitral tribunal.³²⁷ The majority of legal scholars consider decisions from emergency arbitrators to not qualify as awards under the New York Convention.³²⁸ The courts in the United States, however, do allow for such decisions to qualify as awards under the New York

³¹⁹ Nigel Blackaby and others, *Redfern and Hunter on International Arbitration* (Sixth edition, Oxford University Press 2015), par. 9.01. See also: Article 54(1) ICSID Convention.

³²⁰ Blackaby and others (n 319), par. 9.03; Bernd Ehle, ‘New York Convention, Article I [Scope of Application]’, in Reinmar Wolff (ed), *New York Convention: Article-by-Article Commentary* (Second Edition), para. 276; Tony Cole and Pietro Ortolani, *Understanding International Arbitration* (2020), p. 174-175.

³²¹ Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 174-175.

³²² *ibid*, p. 175-177.

³²³ *ibid*, p. 167-174.

³²⁴ Ehle (n 320), par. 62.

³²⁵ Giacomo Marchisio, *The Notion of Award in International Commercial Arbitration: A Comparative Analysis of French Law, English Law, and the UNCITRAL Model Law* (Kluwer Law International 2017) <<http://www.kluwerarbitration.com/book-toc?toc=TOC-Marchisio-2017>>, p. 87-89.

³²⁶ Ehle (n 320), par. 64.

³²⁷ Article 29 ICC Rules; Article 6 ICDR Rules.

³²⁸ Ehle (n 320), par. 71a.

Convention.³²⁹ Partial awards under the rule 39 of the ICSID Rules are not considered awards under the ICSID Convention.³³⁰

When it comes to the enforcement of an award, it must be noted that this aspect only comes into use when one or both of the parties are not complying with the award.³³¹ Once an award is not complied with, the party seeking compliance of the award must find a way to force the non-compliant party to honour the award. As States hold a monopoly on the use of force, one must thus turn to the State to aid in the enforcement of the award. To facilitate such enforcement, States have developed domestic enforcement laws to regulate international commercial arbitration. As mentioned in paragraph 3.2, parties can choose where the arbitral proceedings are legally taking place: the arbitral seat.³³² The arbitration procedure is subject to the laws that apply to arbitration in that State.³³³ Provided that the arbitration was in compliance with the domestic arbitration laws, the party seeking compliance can use the court system of the State in which the arbitration was seated to enforce the award. The power of the State, however, is confined to the areas within its jurisdiction. In order to enforce an award outside the jurisdiction of the seat, one can use the New York Convention. States that are party to the New York Convention are under the general obligation to recognise and enforce foreign arbitral awards.³³⁴ The recognition of an award by the courts of a State grants an award legal effect in that State. Once an award is recognised, it can be enforced by the courts of that State to force the non-compliant party to comply with the award. This allows the party seeking compliance to enforce an award even if it falls outside the jurisdiction of the arbitral seat.

Awards can also be challenged, namely in two ways. Firstly, awards can be annulled in an annulment procedure, which is also referred to as the ‘setting aside’ of the award.³³⁵ An award may only be annulled at the courts of the arbitral seat, on the grounds provided for by the domestic arbitration laws of that seat.³³⁶ Secondly, as an exception to the previously discussed general obligation from the New York Convention, States can refuse to recognise and enforce an award on the grounds provided for by the New York Convention.³³⁷ Over the years, domestic arbitration laws concerning the annulment of awards in jurisdictions worldwide have increasingly aligned with the rules for refusing the recognition and enforcement of awards under the New York Convention. While some differences remain, both challenge procedures can largely be discussed in tandem.³³⁸ When it comes to

³²⁹ *ibid.*

³³⁰ Article 26 ICSID Convention; Gabrielle Kaufmann-Kohler, Aurélia Antonietti and Michele Potesta, ‘24. Interim Relief in Investment Treaty Arbitration’ in Katia Yannaca-Small (ed), *Arbitration under international investment agreements: a guide to the key issues* (Second edition, Oxford University Press 2018), p. 672-674.

³³¹ Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 181.

³³² *ibid.*, p. 29-31.

³³³ *ibid.*, p. 30.

³³⁴ This includes arbitral awards that are not considered domestic awards in the seat of the arbitration. See to that effect: Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 211.

³³⁵ *ibid.*, p. 206-207.

³³⁶ *ibid.*, p. 206-207.

³³⁷ Article V(2)(b) New York Convention.

³³⁸ Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 205-206; Wilinski (n 338), p. 470-471.

international investment arbitration, States that have ratified the ICSID convention must recognise and enforce awards rendered in accordance with that convention.³³⁹ Accordingly, the only way to challenge an international investment award under the ICSID Convention is through the annulment procedure it provides.³⁴⁰

§5.2: Formal requirements for awards and LLMs

The formal requirements for arbitral awards are largely harmonised to the standard set by the New York Convention.³⁴¹ Accordingly, awards must be made in writing. Depending on the jurisdiction, there are other formal requirements for an award, as stated in paragraph 3.4. For example, Article 31(1) of the Model Law requires that the majority of the arbitrators sign the award. Following the judgment of the Yukos case as discussed in paragraph 3.5, it is unlikely that this requirement is violated through the use of an LLM to help draft an award. The signatures are there to attest to the authenticity of the award and, in some jurisdictions, indicate which arbitrators support the delivered award and which did not.³⁴² Consequently, this requirement has no bearing on the use of LLMs in the manner that is central in this paper.

Other formal requirements are that the award contains the date of the award and the place where the arbitration legally took place.³⁴³ This has no bearing on the use of LLMs.

Finally, there is the requirement for an award to contain reasons. Paragraph 3.5 discussed at length how the requirement for an award to contain reasons differs from jurisdiction to jurisdiction. To keep it concise, it was found that reasons remain a mandatory part of an award in the absence of informed and specific consent by the parties to settle a dispute by way of consent award. While Jensen considers that the drafting of reasons is so intertwined with arbitral decision-making that the drafting of reasons must not be delegated to non-arbitrators,³⁴⁴ it has nothing to do meeting the requirement that the award must contain reasons. Indeed, it should be noted that it is widely recognised that an award can only be set aside or refused recognition and enforcement on the basis of this requirement when the reasons are not provided at all, or in rare cases, extremely inconsistent or illogical.³⁴⁵

³³⁹ Articles 53-55 ICSID. Of course, Article 55 ICSID could provide a (partial) exception to this.

³⁴⁰ See Article 53(1) ICSID. For the annulment procedure, see: Article 52 ICSID. See also: Katia Yannaca-Small, '27. Annulment of ICSID Awards: Is It Enough or Is Appeal around the Corner?' in Katia Yannaca-Small (ed), *Arbitration under international investment agreements: a guide to the key issues* (Second edition, Oxford University Press 2018), p. 727-758.

³⁴¹ Philipp Peters, 'Chapter II: The Arbitrator and the Arbitration Procedure - Presiding Arbitrator, Deciding Arbitrator: Decision-Making in Arbitral Tribunals' in Nikolaus Pitkowitz and others (eds), *Austrian yearbook on international arbitration 2011* (Kluwer Law International), p. 153-154.

³⁴² See to that effect: Blackaby and others (n 319), paras. 9.148-9.149; Maxi Scherer, 'New York Convention, Article IV [Formal Requirements for Recognition and Enforcement of Arbitral Awards]' in Reinmar Wolff and others (eds), *New York Convention: Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards of 10 June 1958: article-by-article commentary* (Second edition, Beck 2019), p. 3-4; Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 181-182.

³⁴³ Peters (n 341), p. 154-155; Blackaby and others (n 319), paras. 9.139-9.172.

³⁴⁴ Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 206-208.

³⁴⁵ Peters (n 341), p. 154-155; Blackaby and others (n 319), paras. 9.139-9.172; Yannaca-Small (n 340), p. 741-743.

Consequently, the requirement to provide reasons is easily met.³⁴⁶ Admittedly, when an LLM is used to draft the reasons when it is only provided with the decision itself, it could potentially lead to inconsistent or illogical reasoning. Arbitral tribunals must use LLMs in a responsible manner. Indeed, this thesis covers the situation where arbitral tribunals use LLMs to *help* draft an award, not draft it entirely without any form of supervision or control. If arbitral tribunals use the output of an LLM without verifying the contents, then there could be merit to the arguments that an LLM could potentially detract from the quality of the reasons.³⁴⁷ A diminished quality of reasons could have broader negative effects on the ‘reasons for reasons’, such as legitimacy, precedent and the development of law.³⁴⁸ If the use of LLMs would truly cause such effects in the future, then a more robust quality requirement for awards could be warranted. Until that time, however, there is no reason to assume that a responsible use of an LLM to help draft an award would violate the requirement of an award to provide reasons.

§5.3: The Fourth Arbitrator defence³⁴⁹

The so-called ‘Fourth Arbitrator defence’ stems from claims made by the Russian Federation in the Yukos case. In this case, that was already discussed to an extent in paragraph 3.5, the Russian Federation submitted that the arbitral tribunal acted in excess of its mandate by delegating their personal mandate to a tribunal secretary to such an extent, that the secretary could be viewed as a *de facto* ‘fourth arbitrator’. In the same line of reasoning, the Russian Federation claimed that the arbitral tribunal was not constituted correctly, as the ‘fourth arbitrator’ was neither selected nor appointed by the parties. While the Dutch Supreme Court rejected both claims, it would be interesting to examine how these claims could be applied to the use of LLMs to help draft awards.

It should be noted that while the ICSID Convention does provide for the grounds ‘improper constitution of the tribunal’ and ‘manifest excess of powers’ in its annulment procedure, these grounds are dealt with in a different way than non-ICSID awards. The ground ‘improper constitution of the tribunal’ has rarely been invoked and is considered to be exceedingly vague.³⁵⁰ The ground ‘manifest excess of powers’ covers the situation where a tribunal exceeds the parties’ agreement or consent as ‘jurisdiction.’³⁵¹ This ground is also exceedingly

³⁴⁶ Peters (n 341), p. 154-155.

³⁴⁷ Orlando Federico Cabrera Colorado, ‘The Future of International Arbitration in the Age of Artificial Intelligence’ (2023) 40 *Journal of International Arbitration* 301, p. 335-341.

³⁴⁸ For a collection of such arguments, see: J Ole Jensen, *Tribunal Secretaries in International Arbitration* (First edition, Oxford University Press 2019), p. 204-208; Maxi Scherer, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Legal Decision-Making: The Wide Open?’ [2019] *Journal of International Arbitration* 539, p. X; Colorado (n 347), p. 335-341.

³⁴⁹ *P v Q*, *P v Q* and ors [2017] EWHC 194 (Comm) (High Court, England); Sophia Elisabeth von Dewall, ‘Tribunal Secretaries: How to Prevent a Friend from Turning into a Foe?’ in Filip De Ly and Luc Demeyere (eds), *Arbitral secretaries: reports from the joint NAI-CEPANI colloquium, October 5, 2017* (Wolters Kluwer 2018).

³⁵⁰ Yannaca-Small (n 340), p. 734-735.

³⁵¹ *ibid*, p. 736-737.

rare, as only three ‘full’ awards and two partial awards have been annulled on the basis of jurisdiction.³⁵²

The claim that the arbitral tribunal was not constituted properly, is based on domestic law that converged on Article V(1)(d) of the New York Convention.³⁵³ This article allows States to refuse the recognition and enforcement of awards on the basis of two separate grounds: i) a defect in the composition of the arbitral tribunal or ii) a violation of the applicable arbitral procedure.³⁵⁴ With regard to the first part, the correct composition of the arbitral tribunal is primarily dictated by the agreement of the parties.³⁵⁵ If there is no agreement between the parties, then the composition of the arbitral tribunal is decided by the applicable law of the seat.³⁵⁶ Additionally, if there is an agreement but it leaves ‘gaps’ in the composition of the tribunal, then these gaps must be filled by either a mutually agreed upon specific law to be applied to fill gaps in the agreement, or by the law of the seat.³⁵⁷ It must be mentioned that an agreement on the composition of the arbitral tribunal must be honoured even if it was impliedly made.³⁵⁸ The ‘composition of the arbitral tribunal’ can not only refer to the process of appointing arbitrators or the number of arbitrators, but also to circumstances concerning the individual arbitrators themselves. Such circumstances can include concerns regarding their impartiality or qualifications.³⁵⁹ When it comes to the number of arbitrators, there is plenty of case law on arbitrations conducted by fewer arbitrators than parties (initially) agreed to, so-called ‘truncated tribunals’.³⁶⁰ A truncated tribunal occurs when ‘at least one arbitrator refuses to take part in the deliberations, the voting process or any other significant part of the proceedings’.³⁶¹ Cases where this particular ground is invoked in the allegation that more arbitrators participated than parties agreed to, however, are exceedingly rare and unsuccessful.³⁶² In cases where a party alleges that the arbitral decision was taken by others than the appointed/selected arbitrators, it is more common that the ‘excess of mandate’ is invoked instead.³⁶³ Therefore, it is unlikely that the use of an LLM to help draft an award would fall within the scope of the ‘composition of the arbitral tribunal’.³⁶⁴ Even if it did, there would still be an interesting caveat. Regard must be had for the behaviour of parties

³⁵² *ibid.*

³⁵³ Cf. Articles 36(1)(a)(iv), Article 34(2)(iv) Model Law and Article 1065(1)(b) Dutch CCP (old).

³⁵⁴ Peters (n 341), p. 152.

³⁵⁵ Christian Borris and others, ‘New York Convention, Article V [Grounds for Refusal of Recognition and Enforcement of Arbitral Awards]’, *New York Convention: Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards of 10 June 1958: article-by-article commentary* (Second edition, Beck 2019), paras. 269-274.

³⁵⁶ *ibid.*, paras. 275-278.

³⁵⁷ *ibid.*, para. 276.

³⁵⁸ *ibid.*, para. 277.

³⁵⁹ *ibid.*, paras. 279-328.

³⁶⁰ *ibid.*, paras. 286-288.

³⁶¹ Peters (n 341), p. 145.

³⁶² See to that effect: Jensen (n 348), p. 348-354.

³⁶³ See for example: Hans-Patrick Schroeder and Wolfgang Junge, ‘Tribunal Secretaries Re-Examined—Comparative Legal Framework, Best Practices, and Terms of Appointment’ (2022) 38 *Arbitration International* 21, paras. 2.2.1-2.2.5.

³⁶⁴ See *Yukos*, Supreme Court 5 November 2021, ECLI:NL:HR:2021:1645 (Judgment on high appeal, the Netherlands), para: 5.5.4.

subsequent to the agreement on the composition. If parties agree to compose a tribunal a certain way and subsequently both act contrary to that agreement, it can be assumed that this constitutes a mutually agreed upon modification to that agreement.³⁶⁵ Consider the situation where it is accepted that the use of an LLM to help draft an award somehow affects the ‘composition of the arbitral tribunal’, to the degree that it no longer conforms with the initial agreement between parties. Even then, if the parties then select a ‘busy arbitrator’ as described in paragraph 3.5, it can be assumed that this constitutes a mutually agreed upon modification that allows the arbitrator to use a tribunal secretary or LLM to draft the award. If that does not remedy the supposed ‘defect’ in the composition of the tribunal, then the party seeking recognition and enforcement can still remedy the situation by proving that the improper composition of the arbitral tribunal did not affect the outcome of the arbitration.³⁶⁶ The reason that the onus is on the party seeking recognition and enforcement to prove the aforementioned, is because once a defect in the composition has been established, it is assumed to affect the outcome of the procedure.³⁶⁷

When it comes to the second part of Article V(1)(d), it should be noted that this ground does not exist in the domestic arbitration laws of France, England and the US. In those jurisdictions, violations of the applicable arbitral procedure are caught by the ‘excess of mandate’ challenge ground in annulment procedures.³⁶⁸ Despite this difference, challenges on the basis of a violation of arbitral procedure are applied in a very similar way across all jurisdictions.³⁶⁹ The agreement between the parties is once again the primary standard to determine whether there was a violation of the applicable arbitral procedure.³⁷⁰ Where the parties have provided for a specific set of arbitration rules to apply, this is considered to be the set of arbitration rules in force at the time of the start of the arbitral proceedings.³⁷¹ If there are gaps in the agreement pertaining to procedural aspects, then the mutually agreed upon specific gap-filling law will be applicable. Absent such a choice of law, or absent any agreement between the parties at all, it is the law of the seat that is the standard by which flawed proceedings can be determined.³⁷² There is an additional requirement in order for a deviation from the applicable standard to meet the threshold of a ‘flawed proceeding’.³⁷³ Both referred to as ‘causality’ or ‘gravity’, it boils down to the same thing: did the procedural deviation affect the outcome of the proceedings?³⁷⁴ There have been several cases where the recognition of an award was refused on this particular ground due to the arbitral tribunal fully abdicating both the arbitral decision-making and the drafting of the award to a tribunal

³⁶⁵ Borris and others (n 355), para. 279.

³⁶⁶ *ibid*, paras. 300-304.

³⁶⁷ *ibid*, paras. 304-304a, 319.

³⁶⁸ Wilinski (n 338), p. 470-471.

³⁶⁹ Wilinski (n 338), p. 470-471.

³⁷⁰ Borris and others (n 355), para. 323.

³⁷¹ *ibid*, para. 324b.

³⁷² *ibid*, para. 308-314.

³⁷³ *ibid*, para. 315.

³⁷⁴ *ibid*, para. 321.

expert.³⁷⁵ While the courts considered such ‘total abdication’ a violation of procedure, it would certainly be interesting to know whether other courts agree with the *Yukos* judgment that the drafting of an award by a tribunal secretary by itself does not constitute a (sufficiently serious) breach of arbitral procedure.³⁷⁶ It follows that it would be unlikely that the use of an LLM to help draft an award would lead to the application of this ground for refusal or annulment, provided parties did not agree to exclude such use. As mentioned in the previous paragraph, the subsequent behaviour of parties contrary to the agreement can be assumed to constitute a mutually agreed upon modification to that agreement. In that context, the selection of a ‘busy arbitrator’ could potentially imply party consent for the arbitrator to use an LLM to help draft an award, despite a specific mutually agreed upon exclusion of the use of LLMs before the arbitral proceedings commenced. Additionally, one could consider that a lack of mutually agreed upon exclusion of ancillary means could nowadays be construed as implied consent to its use. Indeed, it is worth repeating that a recent survey showed that 65% of the parties did not care whether arbitrators delegated their tasks to someone else, including tasks such as issuing procedural orders and drafting the award.³⁷⁷ Yet, this argument fails when one considers a recent survey on the use of AI by arbitrators, where 59% of the participants agreed that the use of AI by arbitrators should require prior approval by the parties.³⁷⁸ Finally, it should be remarked that the aforementioned ‘causality’ or ‘gravity’ test would make it exceedingly hard to successfully use this ground to challenge an award drafted with the help of an LLM. Given that the deliberations of the arbitrators are confidential,³⁷⁹ it would be very difficult to prove that the outcome of the arbitration was affected by such use of an LLM. In contrast with the previous part of Article V(1)(d), this ‘causality’ or ‘gravity’ is not assumed and must be proven by the party challenging the award.³⁸⁰

³⁷⁵ In *Sacheri v. Robotto*, arbitrators appointed an expert to make the arbitral decision and draft the award for them. This was of course seen as a violation of the *intuitu personae* principle. See: *Sacheri v. Robotto*, Corte di Cassazione, 2765, 7 June 1989, Y.B. Com. Arb. XVI (1991), 156–157 (Supreme Court, Italy). Additionally, consider the case *Starrett Housing Corp v. Iran*, where the court recalled that the arbitral tribunal should not abdicate its decision-making to a tribunal expert. See: *Starrett Housing Corp v Iran* [1987] 16 Iran–US CTR 112, 197 (Iran–United States Claims Tribunal). Furthermore, consider the case *Twin Lakes Reservoir & Canal Co v. Platt Rogers*, where a court found that there was no indication of such abdication. See: *Twin Lakes Reservoir & Canal Co v Platt Rogers Ltd* 147 P.2d 828, 833 (Colorado Supreme Court, United States of America). Also consider the case where the court held that if the tribunal adopted the conclusions of a third party ‘blindly, or contrary to their own convictions’, they would have been ‘censurable for misconduct sufficient to void their award’, see: *Continental Materials Corp. v Gaddis Mining* 306 F.2d 952 (10th Cir 1962) (Court of Appeals Tenth Circuit, United States), par. 955.

³⁷⁶ *Yukos*, District Court of The Hague 18 February 2020, ECLI:NL:GHDHA:2020:234 (Judgment on appeal, the Netherlands), para. 6.6. Interestingly, the Dutch Supreme Court confirms this and states that one cannot use this ground to challenge the outcome in a ‘roundabout way’. This seems to refer implicitly to a case mentioned in *Borris and others* (n 355), see to that effect: *Yukos*, Supreme Court 5 November 2021, ECLI:NL:HR:2021:1645 (Judgment on high appeal, the Netherlands), para: 5.5.4; *Borris and others* (n 355), para. 340; *International Standard Electric Corporation v Bidas Sociedad Anonima Petrolera*, ‘US No. 115, International Standard Electric Corporation v. Bidas Sociedad Anonima Petrolera, Industrial y Comercial, (Southern District of New York, United States).

³⁷⁷ Thomas Schultz and Robert Kovacs, ‘The Rise of a Third Generation of Arbitrators?: Fifteen Years after Dezalay and Garth’ (2012) 28 *Arbitration International* 161, p. 170-171.

³⁷⁸ De Werra J and others, ‘The Use of AI in International Arbitration Proceedings’ (Digital Law Center, 5 December 2024)

³⁷⁹ *Jensen* (n 348), p. 158-159.

³⁸⁰ *Borris and others* (n 355), para. 318.

Similar to the previous two grounds for the setting aside or refusal of recognition of an award, the ground ‘excess of mandate’ is applied in a rather uniform way when it comes to the delegation of powers.³⁸¹ This is due to convergence on the New York Convention, as mentioned previously.³⁸² In the context of this thesis, this ground could potentially be used to challenge an award on the basis that the arbitral tribunal ‘delegated’ an essential and personal part of its mandate to an LLM. This essential and personal part of its mandate could be considered the drafting in and of itself. It could also be considered the arbitral decision-making with which drafting the award is so intertwined, that the delegation of drafting an award constitutes the delegation of decision-making. It must be recalled that the essential and personal mandate of the arbitrators, the *intuitu personae* principle, is only based on party autonomy. As discussed in paragraphs 3.2-3.7, there are indications that the delegation of drafting an award does not breach the *intuitu personae* principle in and of itself. Some authors even present compelling evidence that in this day and age, parties no longer expect the arbitrators to draft awards without assistance. While the drafting of an award could potentially have some effect on the arbitral decision-making, more research is needed to determine how much influence that is and which tasks could be considered part of the ‘drafting of an award’. In any case, it is apparent from the case law that so far only total abdication of arbitral decision-making has been accepted as a sufficiently serious excess of the tribunal’s mandate.³⁸³

In the light of all the foregoing, one must conclude that as long as the arbitral tribunal retains the final responsibility for the award and does not completely abdicate its decision-making, it will be unlikely that the use of an LLM to help draft an award would constitute a sufficiently serious excess of the tribunal’s mandate.

³⁸¹ Wilinski (n 338), p. 455-456.

³⁸² Wilinski (n 338), p. 455-456.

³⁸³ Schroeder and Junge (n 363), paras. 2.1-3.4.

§5.4: Public Policy and LLMs in challenge procedures

Under the New York Convention, an arbitral award may be set aside if a national court of the seat of arbitration considers that the award is in conflict with the public policy of the seat.³⁸⁴ It should be noted that arbitral awards cannot be set aside on public policy grounds under the ICSID Convention.³⁸⁵ Additionally, the recognition and enforcement of a foreign arbitral award can be refused by the court of the State where recognition and enforcement is sought, if the award is in violation of the public policy of that State.³⁸⁶ The term ‘public policy’ is neither defined in the New York Convention, nor in the Model Law. Despite the efforts of many authors to define it, it is still considered to be a ‘nebulous’ concept in the international commercial arbitration community.³⁸⁷ In the opinion of the author of this thesis, most of the discussions on how to define public policy are of a dogmatic nature and lack practical effect.³⁸⁸ In the context of international arbitration, public policy can essentially be defined as fundamental norms or values in the legal system of a State that this State considers inviolable.³⁸⁹ In order to find out to what extent arbitral tribunals can use an LLM to help draft an award, it must thus be determined whether there are States where such use would violate its public policy. At the time of the writing of this thesis, it appears that the European Union’s ‘Artificial Intelligence Act’ (‘AI Act’) is going to be the world’s first piece of binding legislation that relates to use of AI in international arbitration.³⁹⁰ In fact, the European Commission boasts that the AI Act is the ‘first-ever comprehensive legal framework on AI worldwide.’³⁹¹ While more research is needed to confirm it, it thus seems unlikely that the aforementioned use of LLMs in international arbitration violates any provision of public policy in force in the world at the time of the writing of this thesis.³⁹²

³⁸⁴ Blackaby and others (n 319), para. 10.81.

³⁸⁵ Yannaca-Small (n 340), p. 815.

³⁸⁶ Article V(2)(b) New York Convention.

³⁸⁷ Blackaby and others (n 319), para. 10.84.

³⁸⁸ Somewhat supported by: Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 231-233.

³⁸⁹ Inspired by Blackaby and others (n 319), paras. 10.81-10.88; Cole and Ortolani (n 320), p. 231-233.

³⁹⁰ Gülüm Bayraktaroğlu-Özçelik and Ş Barış Özçelik, ‘Use of AI-Based Technologies in International Commercial Arbitration’ (2021) 12 European Journal of Law and Technology; ‘AI Act | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future’ (23 April 2024) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>> accessed 17 May 2024.

³⁹¹ ‘Use of AI-Based Technologies in International Commercial Arbitration’ (2021) 12 European Journal of Law and Technology; ‘AI Act | Shaping Europe’s Digital Future’ (23 April 2024) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>> accessed 17 May 2024.

³⁹² ‘Could an Arbitral Award Rendered by AI Systems Be Recognized or Enforced? Analysis from the Perspective of Public Policy’ (*Kluwer Arbitration Blog*, 6 February 2020) <<https://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2020/02/06/could-an-arbitral-award-rendered-by-ai-systems-be-recognized-or-enforced-analysis-from-the-perspective-of-public-policy/>> accessed 17 May 2024; Bianca Berardicurti, ‘25. Artificial Intelligence in International Arbitration: The World Is All That Is The Case’.

§5.5: Conclusion

This chapter has covered the risks that could emerge regarding the validity, recognition and enforcement of awards drafted with the help of an LLM. In the two types of challenge procedures against awards, the ‘annulment/setting aside’ procedure and the ‘refusal of recognition and enforcement’ procedure, three major categories were examined. The first category was the formal requirements for awards. It was found that while the use of LLMs to draft awards does not inherently violate formal requirements, some supervision is still warranted to ensure that the award does not contain illogical or inconsistent reasoning. The second category was the ‘fourth arbitrator’ defence. This name originates from the *Yukos* case, where the Russian Federation argued that excessive delegation of decision-making powers to a tribunal secretary effectively created a *de facto* fourth arbitrator. In this category, three separate grounds were examined with respect to the use of an LLM to help draft an award, namely a defect in the composition of the arbitral tribunal, a violation of the applicable arbitral procedure and excess of mandate. As long as arbitral tribunals do not abdicate their decision-making powers entirely, the tribunal’s use of an LLM to help draft an award is unlikely to meet the relatively high threshold for either of those three grounds to successfully challenge an award with. The third and final category was public policy, a concept regarded to be vague by many. While more research is warranted to confirm it, it appears that at the writing of this thesis, there are no provisions of public policy of States around the globe pertaining to the use of an LLM to help draft an award. In conclusion, the current grounds in challenge procedures are unlikely to successfully challenge awards drafted with the help of LLMs.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

The advent of Large Language Models (hereafter: LLMs) has brought about significant change. As this new technology continues to improve, more change is to be expected. This thesis set out to explore the extent and conditions under which a tribunal is allowed to use an LLM to help draft an arbitral award.

First, the fundamental aspects of LLMs were explained. LLMs are advanced computational models capable of generating detailed text-based responses. LLMs are considered to exhibit significant potential for performing a variety of tasks in international arbitration, such as drafting an award or conducting legal research. Despite their capabilities, LLMs are susceptible to inaccuracies, hallucinations and biases, necessitating careful consideration of their application in drafting arbitral awards to ensure the quality, validity, recognition and enforcement of such awards.

The examination of party autonomy-related risks provided insight into the *intuitu personae* principle, which prohibits arbitrators from delegating their personal mandate to someone else. Despite a lack of literature and case law on the use of LLMs to help draft awards, a comparison between LLMs and tribunal secretaries allowed a view as to the application of the *intuitu personae* principle. While drafting parts of an award by a tribunal secretary might not breach the *intuitu personae* principle *per se*, factors could arise that make for an unacceptable influence on the arbitral decision-making. Furthermore, LLMs should not be used when the delegation of drafting an award is explicitly prohibited by the parties.

The exploration of the potential confidentiality-related risks underscored the importance of safeguarding sensitive data. Two primary categories of confidentiality-related risks were identified: the submission of confidential information via prompts and the use of confidential data for training. Within the first category, two potential risks were identified. The first potential risk was whether the submission of a prompt containing confidential information could be considered a disclosure of confidential information to a third party, thereby breaching confidentiality. It was found that where party consent to use an LLM is not provided, nor withheld, the undisclosed use of an LLM by an arbitral tribunal would not constitute a breach of a typical obligation of confidentiality, provided that a similar obligation of confidentiality rests on the publisher or developer of the LLM. The second potential risk was the added risks that emerge when a prompt containing confidential information is submitted to an LLM. It was found that the security of a submitted prompt could never be fully guaranteed. The second category pertains to the risks associated with training LLMs on unredacted awards.

The investigation into the risks relating to the validity, recognition and enforcement of awards drafted with the assistance of LLMs, covered three major categories: formal requirements for awards, the 'fourth arbitrator' defence, and public policy considerations. While LLMs do not inherently breach formal requirements, supervision is still warranted to ensure that the award does not contain extremely illogical or inconsistent reasoning. The 'fourth arbitrator' defence, originating from the Yukos case, relates to challenges to awards on the basis of excessive delegation of decision-making, leading to the idea of a 'fourth arbitrator'. It was concluded that as long as tribunals retain their decision-making authority, the use of LLMs is unlikely to meet the threshold for successful challenges. Mandatory provisions of public policy were found to be no risk for the use of LLMs, as the legislation of States have not yet caught up with the rapid development of LLMs.

In the light of the foregoing, it becomes evident that while LLMs present significant opportunities to arbitral tribunals in international arbitration, their use can pose significant risks too. By ensuring explicit party consent, observing confidentiality obligations and retaining their decision-making authority, arbitral tribunals can steer clear of any issues regarding the validity, recognition and enforceability of their awards drafted with the help of an LLM.

In conclusion, this thesis has navigated the intersection between technological advancement and legal practice, allowing insight into the extent and conditions under which a tribunal is allowed to use an LLM to help draft an arbitral award. As stated in the introduction, the art of progress is to preserve order amid change, and to preserve change amid order. The existing legal framework should not be forgotten, so that we can embrace change and progress.

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